

THE EFFECTS OF PLUG AND PLAY RADIO-BASED INSTRUCTION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF GRADE V LEARNERS IN MATHEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of plug and play radio-based instruction on the performance of Grade V learners in mathematics at G.E. Antonino Memorial Elementary School. The research employed explanatory sequential mixed-methods research design, with a quantitative phase involving pre-test and posttest assessments and a qualitative phase involving interviews with selected six participants. The study included 30 participants, divided equally between the control and experimental groups. Results showed that both groups initially performed poorly on the pre-test but improved to a fair level on the posttest. However, t-test results indicated no significant difference in the performance of learners in mathematics in face-to-face and in instruction supplemented with plug and play RBI. The results showed that the adoption of plug and play radio-based instruction has a minimal impact on the performance of learners in mathematics. Furthermore, the qualitative findings revealed that learners preferred face-to-face instruction over plug and play RBI due to some undermining factors such as the capacity of learners to learn on their own and the style of teachers in delivering audio-recorded lessons. It is recommended that the department may invest in technology resources, conduct further research for refinement, encourage replication and expansion of studies, and collaborate with developers to enhance the quality of educational technology.

Keywords: *Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction, Radio-based Instruction, Mathematics, Audio-recorded Lessons, Learning Activity Sheets*

INTRODUCTION

The closure of educational institutions in response to the COVID-19 pandemic has had unprecedented effects on education worldwide, prompting authorities to propose alternative methods like online learning platforms to ensure students continue learning and prevent the spread of the virus (Abidah et al., 2020). Kapasia et al. (2020) argued that there was a need for innovative teaching methods to overcome mental stress and anxieties during lockdown.

The outbreak prompted a digital revolution, resulting in the widespread adoption of online lectures, teleconferencing, digital open books, online examinations, and virtual interactions (Strielkowski, 2020). However, a significant challenge emerged as many individuals lacked access to technology and the internet. Despite these challenges, efforts were made in the Philippines to create educational opportunities, particularly in rural areas. The Department of Education (DepEd) introduced the plug and play Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) as one of the alternative learning delivery modes for areas without internet access or radio frequency, aiming to reach learners through radio broadcasts (Department of Education, 2021).

The Division of Sarangani has transitioned from printed self-learning modules to Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) coupled with plug and play RBI as a mode of distance learning. This change was made to accommodate the needs of children in remote areas who lack access to smartphones, have poor internet connections, and do not have the necessary gadgets for online study (DepEd Sarangani, 2021). G.E. Antonino Memorial Elementary School, where one of the researchers teaches, is one of the schools that have adopted this learning modality.

The Department of Education has been implementing measures to ensure the continuity of education amidst the challenges brought by the new normal situation. Secretary Leonor Magtolis-Briones emphasized the commitment of the department to prioritizing student welfare and maintaining the quality of education (Arbutante, 2020). To address the limitations of face-to-face learning, the DepEd introduced the Basic Education Learning Community Plan (BE-LCP) for the 2020–2021 school year, aiming to provide accessible and quality education at all levels despite the constraints imposed by the pandemic (DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020). The department enhanced the utilization of television and radio-based resources to support blended learning during the subsequent academic year (2021–2022).

Thus, the researchers conducted a study to investigate the implementation of radio-based instruction, specifically the offline use of radio. While most studies focused on online learning, this research aimed to explore the effects of plug and play radio-based instruction on the academic performance of Grade V learners in mathematics.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effects of plug and play radio-based instruction on the performance in mathematics of Grade V learners of G.E. Antonino Memorial Elementary School in Kiamba 1 District for the school year 2022-2023. More precisely, the researchers aimed to address the following questions:

1. What is the pre-test mean score of the control group?
2. What is the pre-test mean score of the experimental group?
3. Is there a significant difference on the pre-test mean scores between the control and experimental groups?
4. What is the posttest mean score of the control group?
5. What is the posttest mean score of the experimental group?
6. Is there a significant difference on the posttest mean scores between the control and experimental groups?
7. Is there a significant difference between pre-test and posttest mean scores of the control group?
8. Is there a significant difference between pre-test and posttest mean scores of the experimental group?
9. How do learners from the control group describe their experiences on face-to-face instruction?
10. How do the learners from the experimental group describe their experiences on plug and play radio-based instruction?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized an explanatory sequential mixed-methods research design, encompassing two distinctive phases, to examine the effects of plug and play radio-based instruction on the performance of Grade V learners in mathematics. In phase 1, quantitative data was collected through a quasi-experimental approach, with 15 learners in the control group and 15 in the experimental group. Pre-test and posttest data were collected using a researcher-made test. Before administering the instrument, the researchers conducted a pilot test with a group involving 20 learners at the school to test its reliability. The pilot test yielded a Cronbach alpha value of 0.70, described as acceptable. The rating indicated an acceptable capacity of the instrument to accurately measure the performance of the respondents with strength and reliability. The test instrument assessed the performance of the learners during the first grading period from August to October 2022, yielding comprehensive quantitative data.

All the data in this research underwent normality testing using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S test), assuring that all the data were normal. The study analyzed the collected data using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods and thematic analysis. Descriptive statistics calculated the mean scores of Mathematics learners in the control and experimental groups based on their pre-test and posttest performance. Inferential

statistics tested the four hypotheses using t-tests for independent and dependent samples. All of the hypotheses underwent testing with a significance level set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

In phase 2, qualitative data was obtained through interviews with six selected research participants for the Key Informants Interview (KII): three learners from each group. The qualitative data was meticulously organized through thematic analysis following the Collaizi's method as mentioned by Kumar and Grace (2023), which aimed to provide depth and triangulate results from the quantitative data. After data analysis, the researchers integrated both quantitative and qualitative data to make a comprehensive summary of the findings, highlighting the significant impact of plug and play radio-based instruction on the academic performance of Grade V learners in mathematics.

This study was conducted at G.E. Antonino Memorial Elementary School in Kiamba 1 District of the Division of Sarangani. School is classified as a medium school, with 329 total enrollees, 14 teachers, one (1) administrative assistant, and one (1) school head in S.Y. 2022-2023. The school is situated at Linek, Nalus, Kiamba, Sarangani Province. This study is delimited on the effects of plug and play radio-based instruction on the performance in mathematics of the learners in Grade V.

RESULTS

Pre-test Mean Score of the Control Group

In this study, face-to-face instruction, along with learning activity sheets, were employed to teach the control group. The performance of the learners in Mathematics during the pre-test was assessed by calculating the mean score. Table 1 shows the result.

Table 1
Pre-test Mean Score of the Control Group

Interval Scores	F	%	Description
1. 26-30	0	0.00	Excellent
2. 21-25	0	0.00	Very Good
3. 16-20	0	0.00	Good
4. 11-15	2	13.33	Fair
5. 6-10	8	53.33	Poor
6. 1-5	5	33.33	Very Poor
Overall Mean Score		7.00	Poor

The pre-test mean score of the control group is depicted in Table 1.

Pre-test Mean Score of the Experimental Group

The experimental cohort of the study received face-to-face instruction along with the learning activity sheets and with the aid of radio-based instruction. To ascertain the mathematics performance of learners in the experimental cohort with the aid of radio-based instruction during pre-test, the mean was calculated. Table 2 shows the result.

Table 2
Pre-test Mean Score of the Experimental Group

Interval Scores	F	%	Description
1. 26-30	0	0.00	Excellent
2. 21-25	0	0.00	Very Good
3. 16-20	0	0.00	Good
4. 11-15	2	13.33	Fair
5. 6-10	8	53.33	Poor
6. 1-5	5	33.33	Very Poor
Overall Mean Score		7.13	Poor

Table 2 displays the pre-test mean score for the experimental group.

Significant Difference on the Pre-test Mean Scores Between the Control and Experimental Group

At the start of the experiment, similar pre-tests were administered to both the control and the experimental cohort, ensuring a baseline for comparison of their initial knowledge levels. The pre-test findings were statistically analyzed using an independent sample t-test to determine whether the two groups exhibited similarity, as shown in Table 3, facilitating a thorough understanding of any initial differences between the groups.

Table 3
Significant Difference on the Pre-test Mean Scores Between the Control and Experimental Group

Group	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Control	7.00	-0.138	0.891	Not Significant
2. Experimental	7.13			

The difference in the mean scores from the pre-test is highlighted in Table 3 for both the control and experimental groups.

Posttest Mean Score of the Control Group

Face-to-face instruction, along with learning activity sheets, was utilized to teach mathematics to the control group, ensuring a comprehensive educational approach. The learners' performance during the posttest was assessed using the mean calculation, and the results are displayed in Table 4, which provides quantitative data to complement the qualitative insights gained through thematic analysis in Table 9.

Table 4
Posttest Mean Score of the Control Group

Interval Scores	F	%	Description
1. 26-30	0	0.00	Excellent
2. 21-25	0	0.00	Very Good
3. 16-20	1	6.67	Good
4. 11-15	9	60.00	Fair
5. 6-10	5	33.33	Poor
6. 1-5	0	0.00	Very Poor
Overall Mean Score		11.53	Fair

Table 4 presents the mean score of the control group in the posttest.

Posttest Mean Score of the Experimental Group

Mathematics was taught to the experimental group through a combination of face-to-face and plug and play radio-based instruction along with learning activity sheets. The posttest was used to assess the performance of learners in Mathematics within the experimental group with plug and play radio-based instruction assistance, and the mean score was computed. The outcome is presented in table 5.

Table 5
Posttest Mean Score of the Experimental Group

Interval Scores	F	%	Description
1. 26-30	0	0.00	Excellent
2. 21-25	0	0.00	Very Good
3. 16-20	4	26.67	Good

4. 11-15	7	46.67	Fair
5. 6-10	4	26.67	Poor
6. 1-5	0	0.00	Very Poor
Overall Mean Score		12.53	Fair

Table 5 displays the experimental group's posttest mean score.

Significant Difference on the Posttest Mean Scores Between the Control and Experimental Group

At the end of the experiment, similar posttests were administered to both the experimental and control groups. To determine whether the two groups were similar, a t-test for independent samples was used to look at the posttest results statistically. The results of this t-test are certainly displayed in Table 6.

Table 6
Significant Difference on the Posttest Mean Scores Between the Control and Experimental Group

Group	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Control	11.53	-1.148	0.261	Not Significant
2. Experimental	12.53			

Table 6 shows the disparity in posttest mean scores between the control and the experimental group.

Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest Mean Scores of the Control Group

In this study, the control group was simply taught Mathematics using face-to-face instruction along with the learning activity sheets. To determine any significant improvement in the performance of the learners in the control group, a t-test for dependent samples was used. Table 7 shows the result.

Table 7
Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest
Mean Scores of the Control Group

Category	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Pre-test	7.00	-6.513	0.000	Significant
2. Posttest	11.53			

Table 7 presents the difference between the pre-test and posttest mean scores among the control group.

Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental Group

The experimental group in this study was taught Mathematics using face-to-face instruction along with the learning activity sheets with the aid of plug and play radio-based instruction. To determine if the performance of the learners improved with the use of plug and play radio-based instruction, a t-test for independent samples was used. Table 8 shows the result.

Table 8
Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest
Mean Scores of the Experimental Group

Category	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Pre-test	7.13	-8.663	0.000	Significant
2. Posttest	12.53			

Table 8 presents the difference in mean scores between the pre-test and posttest among the experimental group.

Experiences of the Control Group Learners about the Face-to-face Instruction

This study explores the complex web of experiences, perceptions, and challenges encountered by learners engaged in face-to-face instruction. The thematic analysis in Table 9 shows what the learners in the control group had to say about face-to-face instruction. This provides everyone with a better understanding of the various factors that influence how learners learn in traditional classrooms. In the end, the results may add to a deeper understanding of the intricate interactions that occur in face-to-face instruction

between learners, educators, and learning settings, highlighting the importance of personal engagement and real-time feedback.

Table 9
Experiences of the Control Group Learners about the Face-to-face Instruction

Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency of Response
Interaction and Engagement	Social Interaction	General
	Hands-on Activities	General
	Teacher and Peer Support	Typical
Learning Support	Structured Learning	Typical
	Clear Explanations	General
	Supportive Environment	General
	Improved Focus and Comprehension	Typical
Sense of Community	Community Feeling	General
	Teacher-Learner Bond	General
	Cooperation and Teamwork	General

Table 9 presents the experiences of control group learners about the face-to-face instruction. As the researchers carefully looked into the descriptions of experiences of the learners in the control group about face-to-face instruction, the three main themes emerged, namely: interaction and engagement; learning support; and sense of community. The first major theme, interaction and engagement, highlights what a holistic and a well-rounded learning environment has offered to learners as reflected through social interaction, hands-on activities, and teacher and peer support. The second major theme, which is the learning support, underscores what a guided learning has offered to learners as evident in a structured learning, clear explanations, supportive environment, and improved focus and comprehension. And in the third major theme, sense of community, highlights the social and emotional aspects of education where learners learn best through collaboration as seen in the core ideas: community feeling, teacher-learner bond, and cooperation and teamwork.

Experiences of the Experimental Group Learners about the Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction

The thematic analysis focused on the description of experiences of the learners from the experimental group about plug and play radio-based instruction.

Table 10
Experiences of the Experimental Group Learners about
the Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction

Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency of Response
Perceived Value of RBI	Reviewing Lessons	Typical
	Value in the Absence of Teacher	General
	Replay for Better Understanding	General
Flexibility and Accessibility	Convenience of Access	Typical
	Access from Anywhere	General
	Replacing Classroom Facilitation	General
Benefits of Audio Instruction	Less Exhausting for Readers	General
	Enhancing Understanding	General
	Beneficial for Non-Readers	Typical
	Listening Anywhere	General
Comparing Face-to-face and RBI	Effectiveness Comparison	General
	Concerns about Cheating	Typical
	Taking Notes	Typical
Challenges and Criticisms of RBI	Dissatisfaction with RBI	General
	Critique of Instruction Speed	Typical
	Reluctance to Answer Questions	Typical

Table 10 shows the experiences of experimental group learners about the plug and play radio-based instruction. Upon the careful analysis of the researchers unto the descriptions of experiences of the learners in the experimental group about plug and play radio-based instruction, five main themes emerged, namely: perceived value of RBI; flexibility and accessibility; benefits of audio instruction; comparing face-to-face and RBI; and challenges and criticisms of RBI.

The first major theme, perceived value of RBI, highlights the capacity of RBI as a tool for consolidating knowledge which enable learners to engage with lessons at their own pace and reinforcing their understanding as manifested in reviewing lessons, value in the absence of teacher, and replay for better understanding. The second major theme, which is the flexibility and accessibility, reveals the dynamic and transformative nature of a technology-assisted learning platform which is reflected through convenience of access, access from anywhere, and replacing classroom facilitation. The third major theme, benefits of audio instruction, emphasizes the supremacy of technology-assisted learning platform like RBI to provide an inclusive, accessible, and enriching educational experience for learners as revealed in the core ideas: less exhausting for readers, enhancing understanding, beneficial for non-readers, and listening anywhere. The fourth major theme, comparing face-to-face and RBI, provides valuable insights to educational

system to adapt to the preferences and needs of individual learners in an era where traditional classroom instruction and technology-assisted learning platforms like RBI coexists. The recollections of the informants draw comparison between face-to-face instruction and RBI reflected in the core ideas: effectiveness comparison, concerns about cheating, and taking notes. And the fifth major theme, challenges and criticisms of RBI, which offers valuable insights into the complexities of integrating technology into the learning process and the importance of adapting educational platforms to meet the diverse needs and preferences of learners as shown in the core ideas: dissatisfaction with RBI, critique of instruction speed, and reluctance to answer questions.

Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

A comprehensive summary of the quantitative and qualitative findings is presented in Tables 11 and 12. These tables provide a detailed overview of the results of the study, highlighting the significant impact of plug and play radio-based instruction on the academic performance of Grade V mathematics learners. The analysis on the combined data from both the control and experimental groups not only provided statistical information, but also included the experiences of learners, enhancing and confirming the conclusions made. The data may then reveal how the inclusion of plug and play radio-based instruction impacts the performance of the learners in mathematics.

Table 11
Summary Table of Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Findings of the Control Group on the Effects of Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction on the Performance of Grade V Learners in Mathematics

Indicators		Quantitative Findings			Qualitative Findings	Codes
		Pre-test	Posttest	Remarks		
Significant Difference on the Mean Scores	Control Group	7.00	11.53	Significant	<p>We are happy in face-to-face... Even though math is a tough subject, we still learn something because ...we can answer it collaboratively, then ... the teacher can check it right away, giving us instant feedback on whether our answer is correct or not. That is why we learn better in our lesson.</p> <p>We help our classmates if they cannot understand. I will ... explain to them how I ... got the answer. If ever we have assignments or lessons that are unclear... we...review our lesson and help one another by discussing our ideas with one another.</p> <p>The teacher can answer me easily if I ever have questions. I like answering and reading because I know that there is someone who will teach me if I ever make a mistake.</p>	<p>FL3, L263 FL1, L103-107</p> <p>FL1, L134-139</p> <p>FL2, L224-226</p>

Table 11 shows the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings of the significant difference in the mean scores of the control group in pre-test and posttest performance in mathematics which provide valuable insights on the effectiveness of the use of face-to-face instruction on the performance of Grade V learners.

Table 12
Summary Table of Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Findings
of the Experimental Group on the Effects of Plug and Play
Radio-based Instruction on the Performance
of Grade V Learners in Mathematics

Indicators		Quantitative Findings			Qualitative Findings	Codes
		Pre-test	Posttest	Remarks		
Significant Difference on the Mean Scores	Experimental Group	7.13	12.53	Significant	When there is no teacher... because they go somewhere to attend important events like seminars...RBI with LAS is the one teaching us in order ... to answer those we do not understand in what we read while we listen. In the absence of a teacher, we can still easily understand because we can play the lessons in RBI and it is the one teaching us.	RL1, L380-387
					Even if there is no radio frequency signal, we can still listen to the recorded lessons saved on a USB flash drive...repeatedly whenever we want to; we just plug it into the radio distributed to us from school to play the lessons and we can listen to it...following what was written in the LAS... You can still listen to the lessons even if you are far from the gadget or radio. You can carry the radio transistor wherever you go since it is small and not heavy.	RL1, L344-351 RL2, L517-519
					If I will be given a chance to choose, I don't like RBI, face to face is even more meaningful...because there is a teacher who explains. In RBI, there is no teacher present to further explain how to do the module if ever I have other questions to ask... RBI has helped me, but just a little. I reluctantly answer the questions that follow since I have no choice but to answer just to pass the subject.	RL3, L575-579, L598-600

Table 12 shows the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings of the significant difference in the mean scores of the experimental group in pre-test and posttest performance in mathematics which provide valuable insights on the effectiveness of the use of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) on the performance of Grade V learners.

DISCUSSION

Pre-test Mean Score of the Control Group

The pre-test mean score of the control group is depicted in Table 1. The findings indicate that out of 15 respondents, two (2) or 13.33% scored within 11-15 in the 30-item test described as fair; eight (8) or 53.33% scored within 6-10 described as poor; five (5) or

33.33% scored within 1-5 described as very poor but no one scored within 26–30, excellent; 21-25, very good; 16–20, good; and 11–15, fair. Overall, a mean score of 7.00 was achieved by the control group on the pre-test, which is characterized as poor.

The result implies that learners in the control cohort who are taught using face-to-face instruction along with learning activity sheets generally perform poor in mathematics. It corroborates the assertion made by Casinillo (2019), who identified the following five variables as the primary causes of students' mathematics failure rates: poor study habits, unfavorable learning attitudes, social environment, emotional issues, and financial issues. The study found that pupils' study habits are the primary determinant of their failure rate. The sum of the factors affects students' performance more than the specifics of the math courses and the math teacher's method of instruction. Regardless of the mathematics teacher's teaching style, factors such as the student's effort, study habits, and capability may constrain their performance.

Pre-test Mean Score of the Experimental Group

Table 2 displays the pre-test mean score for the experimental group. The data reveal that out of 15 respondents, two (2) or 13.33% scored within 11-15 in the 30-item test described as fair; eight (8) or 53.33% scored within 6-10 described as poor; five (5) or 33.33% scored within 1-5 described as very poor but no one scored within 26–30, excellent; 21-25, very good; 16–20, good; and 11–15, fair. Overall, the pre-test mean score for the experimental group exhibit an average of 7.13, which is described as poor.

The result shows that students in the experimental cohort generally exhibit poor performance in mathematics. The outcome supports the idea reported by Mabena et al. (2021), signifying that several factors exerted an influence on students' self-assurance and academic achievement. Among these factors affecting mathematical performance were aspects attributed to the learners themselves, such as lack of discipline, language barriers, and their attitudes towards learning.

Significant Difference on the Pre-test Mean Scores Between the Control and Experimental Group

The difference in the mean scores from the pre-test is highlighted in Table 3 for both the control and experimental groups. Based on the table, a pre-test mean score of 7.00 was obtained by the control group, while a nearly identical mean score of 7.13 was achieved by the experimental group. It showed that their mean difference of 0.13 was very small. This indicates a lack of significance since the obtained t-value of -0.138 resulted in a p-value greater than 0.05 ($p = 0.891$). This means that there was no substantial disparity in the pre-test mean scores between the control and experimental groups. Since the pre-test mean scores of the two groups were not significantly different, it may be concluded that the two groups were equivalent and the study was conducted with the same level of performance among learners in each grouping. This similarity in the result guarantees that whatever changes in test results later on may be traced back to the methods of instruction used rather than from the starting performance levels.

Consequently, the baseline equivalence between the groups validated the comparative analysis of the study. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that there was no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores between the control and experimental groups is now accepted.

The result supports the conclusions drawn by Alabdulaziz and Tayfour (2023), indicating that there were no statistically significant distinctions in learning mathematical concepts with regard to traditional in-person instruction and remote distance learning methods, with students' outcomes being nearly identical.

Posttest Mean Score of the Control Group

Table 4 presents the mean score of the control group in the posttest. The results show that out of 15 respondents, one (1) or 6.67% scored within 16–20 in the 30-item test described as good; nine (9) or 60%, scored within 11–15 described as fair; five (5) or 33.33%, scored within 6-10 described as poor but no one scored within 26–30, excellent; 21-25, very good; and 1-5, very poor. Overall, a mean score of 11.53 was achieved by the control group in the posttest, which was described as fair.

The result implies that, with face-to-face instruction, learners in the control group continued to exhibit fair Mathematics performance during the first quarter. It confirms the idea stated by Chand et al. (2021) that learners expressed a lack of enthusiasm for mathematics. It has been ascertained that the unsatisfactory performance in the subject is primarily attributed to a deficient mathematics curriculum within educational institutions. Furthermore, a substantial contributor to students' diminished interest and resultant underachievement has been identified as the inadequacy and lack of competence among many school teachers in imparting mathematical knowledge.

Posttest Mean Score of the Experimental Group

Table 5 displays the experimental group's posttest mean score. The results show that out of 15 respondents, four (4) or 26.67% scored within 16–20 in the 30-item test described as good; seven (7) or 46.67%, scored within 11–15 described as fair; four (4) or 26.67%, scored within 6-10 described as poor, but no one scored within 26-30, excellent; 21–25, very good; and 1–5, very poor. Overall, the achieved posttest mean score of the experimental group is 12.53, which falls within the category of fair performance.

The result implies that learners in the experimental group showed little or moderate improvement or fair performance in Mathematics in the first grading period using face-to-face instruction with the aid of plug and play radio-based instruction. This upholds the conclusions drawn by Bermejo et al. (2022), which indicated that the performance of learners in Mathematics exhibited growth and enhancement following the implementation of interactive radio teaching. Learners themselves described their experiences as engaging and highly supported, despite the absence of face-to-face interaction.

Significant Difference on the Posttest Mean Scores Between the Control and Experimental Group

Table 6 shows the disparity in posttest mean scores between the control and the experimental group. In table 6, it can be observed the posttest mean scores, indicating that the control group achieved an average score of 11.53, while the experimental group outperformed them with a mean score of 12.53, resulting in a difference of 1.00. Notably, the t-test analysis indicates that this 1.00 difference is statistically non-significant, as the calculated t-value of -1.148 corresponds to a p-value greater than 0.05 ($p = 0.261$).

The outcome indicates that there was no statistically significant difference in the performance of learners in mathematics who were solely exposed to face-to-face instruction compared to learners exposed to face-to-face instruction combined with plug and play radio-based instruction. With this result, it may be inferred that the use of plug and play radio-based instruction has very little effect on the performance of learners in mathematics.

Thus, the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no significant difference in the posttest mean scores between the control and experimental groups, is accepted. The findings align with the research of Paul and Jefferson (2019), which indicated that there is no notable disparity in student performance between distance learners and those engaged in face-to-face (F2F) instruction, regardless of gender or class rank.

Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest Mean Scores of the Control Group

Table 7 presents the difference between the pre-test and posttest mean scores among the control group. Based on the table, the control group, consisting of 15 learners, got a mean score of 7.00 on the pre-test in Mathematics. After using the face-to-face instruction on the different topics in the first quarter, the control group got a mean posttest score of 11.53. This was higher compared to the pre-test mean score.

Using the t-test on the pre-test and posttest mean scores of the control group, the obtained t-value is -6.513, and since $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.000$), then the difference between the pre-test and posttest scores is significant. This means that with the use of face-to-face instruction, there was a significant improvement in the performance of the learners in mathematics. The null hypothesis, therefore, that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and posttest mean scores of the control group when face-to-face instruction was used, is hereby rejected.

The result implies that learners in face-to-face instruction showed significant improvement in their performance in mathematics. This was supported by Hobri et al. (2018), who found the Learning Together model has a noteworthy impact on students' mathematics achievement and their attitudes towards mathematics. The results showed that because of effective group formation, members' cooperation in supporting one another's learning,

and their sincerity toward teachers' incentives during the treatment period, the Learning Together model helped students' mathematical performance develop.

Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest Mean Scores of the Experimental Group

Table 8 presents the difference in mean scores between the pre-test and posttest among the experimental group. Based on the table, the experimental group, consisting of 15 learners, got a mean of 7.13 on the pre-test in mathematics. After using the face-to-face instruction with the aid of plug and play radio-based instruction on the different topics in the first quarter, the experimental group got a mean posttest score of 12.53. This was higher compared to the pre-test mean score.

Using the t-test on the pre-test and posttest mean scores of the experimental group, the obtained t-value is -8.663, and since $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.000$), then the difference between the pre-test and posttest scores is significant. This means that with the use of face-to-face instruction along with the aid of plug and play radio-based instruction, there was a significant improvement in the performance of the learners in mathematics.

The null hypothesis, therefore, that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and posttest mean scores of the experimental group when face-to-face instruction was used along with plug and play radio-based instruction is hereby rejected.

The result infers that learners in face-to-face instruction along with plug and play radio-based instruction showed significant improvement in their performance in mathematics. This was supported by the findings of Khadija (2020), who noted that millennials and centennials students have inseparable connection with technology and exhibited positive attitudes towards educational radio. Students perceived radio educational broadcasts as a supplementary tool for learning rather than a direct replacement for in-person instruction, which significantly influenced the learning outcomes of students.

Experiences of the Control Group Learners about the Face-to-face Instruction

Interaction and Engagement

The theme of Interaction and Engagement stands as a foundation of the traditional face-to-face classroom environment, emphasizing the importance of social dynamics in the learning process. In a learning environment, interaction is essential to complete the task. It makes teaching and learning more efficient and can help students become better communicators. It highlights how the pupils engage with the teacher, with one another, and even with the entire class. Havik and Westergard (2019) examined the associations between students' views of classroom interactions and their emotional and behavioral engagement. The findings demonstrated that students who viewed classroom interactions as high quality had higher levels of engagement in school. Furthermore, it was observed that instructors' emotional support displayed the most robust correlation

with engagement at both primary and secondary levels. It was found that at the core of effective teaching, learning, and student involvement are positive teacher-student relationships.

Social Interaction. The aspect of social interaction is one of the defining features of face-to-face instruction, especially for learners in control group. Within the walls of a physical classroom and school vicinity, learners have the opportunity to engage in profound and meaningful social interactions. This interpersonal exchange is at the core of their educational experience, fostering not only a sense of belonging but also enriching their learning journey. As all of the participants shared:

FL3: *Kanang lipay gyud kayo ko sa skul sir kay naa akong mga amigo, mga klasmeyts, ug teachers, naa koy kauban magtuon...(Lines 256-257)*
(I am very happy at school because I have my friends, classmates, and teachers, I have companions in learning.)

FL1: *Ganahan ko sa paglibot-libot sa eskwelahan sir kay sa balay ako ra unya boring. Diri sa eskwelahan sir inig kahuman sa klase pwede pa ka makalibot-libot, daghan kayo kag bata makit-an nga dati mga klasmeyts, mga lain lain nga grade makadula nimu... maglaag-laag uban akong mga klasmeyts, mga barkada. (Lines 88-95)*
(I love roaming around the school, sir, because at home I am just alone and I feel so bored. Here in school, sir, after class we can roam around, where we see many children, some of whom were my classmates before, children from different grade levels whom we can play with... strolling with my classmates and friends.)

FL2: *...Dili boring sa skul sir kay daghan mga bata, mga klasmeyts, makadula-dula mi...nagasulat, naa ko mapangutanahan, naa pud mga titser makatudlo sa amoa. (Lines 215-217)*
(It is not boring in school, sir, there are lots of kids and classmates where we can play together. We write; I have someone to ask; I also have teachers who will teach us.)

Control group learners expressed how social interaction in face-to-face instruction has benefited them in several ways, such as through meaningful discussions. Learners have engaged in live, real-time discussions, asked questions, sought clarifications, and gained deeper insights into the subject matter. These discussions enhanced their understanding, critical thinking, and analytical skills. Building friendships and a supportive network is another advantage of face-to-face instruction. Learners had the opportunity to connect with peers, share ideas, and collaborate on group work, creating a sense of camaraderie that enhanced their educational experience. These social connections contribute to emotional well-being, motivation, and a shared sense of purpose in their academic journey.

Bahtiar et al. (2021) highlighted the crucial role of the presence and support of classmates at school in the social interaction of primary school learners, which directly impacts their academic success. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as "peer effects." Learners are more inclined to engage in collaborative efforts with high-achieving learners over school-related issues. Exceptional learners have the ability to make significant contributions to their educational performance, leading to enhanced academic accomplishment, more favorable career choices, and ultimately better labor market outcomes in the future. These good peers can also offer constructive comments to their

peers regarding their abilities and performance in a classroom setting. Hence, the social connection among peers exerts substantial impacts on the conduct, personality, and academic achievement of learners.

Hands-on Activities. Hands-on activities are very evident in a face-to-face instruction which plays a vital role in enriching the learning experience of learners in control group. The activities work as an interface between academic concepts and real-world use, allowing learners to participate in and fully experience the subject matter actively.

Hands-on activities offer a tangible way for learners to connect with the subject matter. Through direct participation, learners gain a deeper understanding of concepts and are better equipped to grasp complex theoretical knowledge. It also promotes curiosity and critical thinking as students actively explore and analyze their findings, enhancing their problem-solving skills. It is evident in the narratives of all the participants:

FL3: *Kanang lipay mi sa face-to-face sir kay nagahimu mi ug arts, nagasulat mi ug nakatuon ug mas nakasabot mi sa amoang leksiyon labi na sa Math. (Lines 263-265)*
(We are happy in face-to-face, sir, because we are doing arts, we are writing and we learn and understand better the lessons, especially in Math.)

FL2: *Sa face-to-face, sir, ginapagroup activity mi sa amoang teacher, naga-answer mi, nagasulat, nagabasa, ug nagadula. (Lines 219-221)*
(In face-to-face, sir, teachers gave us group activities; we answer, we write, we read, and we play.)

FL1: *Kanang baski lisod ang Math sir, nakatuon gihapon mi kay naa man mga group activities nga ginapahimu nga magtinabangay mig answer, tapos answeran dayon namu sa board unya macheck dayon sa titser kung tama ba o mali ang among answer maong mas makasabot mi sa lesson... (FL1, Lines 103-107)*
(Even though Math is a tough subject, sir, we still learn something because there are group activities that are given to us where we can answer it collaboratively, and then after answering it, the teacher will check it right away, giving us instant feedback on whether our answer is correct or not. That is why we learn better in our lesson.)

In hands-on learning, learners shared how they were subjected to group activities that encourage collaboration, teamwork, and communication skills that are highly transferable to real-world scenarios. Working together on a task allows learners to combine their individual strengths and knowledge, creating a rich and multifaceted learning experience. These collaborative endeavors also promote creativity and innovation as learners explore diverse solutions and ideas. It is really true that these first-hand experiences of learners provided them sense of accomplishment and help them develop practical skills that can be applied in their future careers.

Also, these activities not only deepen their understanding of academic content but also equip them with essential life skills, making face-to-face instruction a holistic and invaluable educational approach. The research carried out by Sulyman et al. (2022) strengthened this claim as hands-on activities demonstrated significant effect in academic performance of pupils in Basic Science. Hands-on activities can bring about improvement in the academic performance of pupils regardless of gender. Additionally, the study

revealed that those exposed to hands-on activities in private schools performed significantly higher than those exposed to hands-on activities in public schools.

Teacher and Peer Support. Teacher and peer support are critical components of the face-to-face instruction experience, providing learners in control group with valuable resources to enhance their educational journey. This dynamic support system ensures that learners have immediate access to assistance when needed, fostering inclusivity and a sense of camaraderie in the classroom. This is reflected in the testimonies shared by some participants:

FL3: *Kung naa koy mga pangutana ug wala nasabtan sa lesson sir kay makapangutana ko direktso sa akoang teacher ug sa akoo pud na mga klasmeys...* (Lines 270-272)
(If ever I have questions that are not understood in the lesson, sir, I can directly ask my teacher and also my classmates.)

FL2: *Matubag dayon ko sa ako teacher kung naa koy pangutana. Ganahan ko mag-answer ug magbasa kay kabalo ko naay magtudlo sa akoo kung mamali man ko...* (Lines 224-226)
(The teacher can answer me easily if I ever have questions. I like answering and reading because I know that there is someone who will teach me if I ever make a mistake.)

One of the primary advantages learners have experienced in face-to-face instruction is the direct access to teachers. In a traditional classroom setting, learners can easily approach their teachers for clarification, guidance, or additional explanations. This immediate feedback is instrumental in helping learners overcome challenging concepts or topics that promote a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The personal rapport developed between teachers and learners often results in a nurturing and encouraging learning environment where no question is too trivial and no learner is left behind.

In addition to teacher support, face-to-face instruction encourages peer support. Learners in control groups can form study groups or collaborate with classmates to enhance their understanding of the material. These collaborative efforts enable learners to explain concepts to each other in simpler terms, offer alternative perspectives, and provide emotional support during challenging times. This sense of community and shared learning fosters a feeling of inclusivity and belonging, ensuring that students are not isolated in their educational journey. As FL1 shared:

FL1: *...Ginatabangan namu amoang klasmeys kung naa silay wala nasabtan. Gina-explain pud naku kung giunsa naku pag-answer ug kung paunsa naku nakuha ang answer. Kung naa me assignments o naa leksiyon nga dili kayo namu nasabtan, nagagrupo-grupo mi para ireview to nga lesson, ug nagatabangay mi, ginadiscuss namu amo mga ideas.* (Lines 134-139)
(We help our classmates if they cannot understand. I will also explain to them how I answered or got the answer. If ever we have assignments or lessons that are unclear to us, we gather together to review our lesson and help one another by discussing our ideas with one another.)

The accessibility to teacher and peer support in the face-to-face classroom setting is a fundamental aspect of the traditional educational experience. It ensures that learners can seek assistance and clarification when needed, promoting a deeper understanding of the material and a sense of inclusivity and camaraderie among learners. These support

systems contribute to the holistic development of learners and are key features of the enduring value of in-person education.

The study conducted by Martinot et al. (2022) emphasized that in our society, encouraging learners to participate in their education is a top priority. The research has demonstrated that the social support learners receive from their immediate sources can greatly contribute to their level of involvement. Based on the study, the level of perceived support from the mother was greater compared to that from the father, teachers, and peers. Learners residing in the priority education region reported receiving greater support from their teachers compared to their peers residing in the more advantaged location. An investigation using path modeling revealed that every form of social support, with the exception of assistance from mothers, had a positive impact on school participation. Peers and teachers were shown to be the most effective sources of support for school involvement.

Learning Support

Learning support plays an essential role in the context of face-to-face instruction. This holistic concept encompasses various aspects that contribute to an enriched and structured learning journey. One of the key benefits of learning support in traditional classrooms is the ease of learning. Learners in control groups often find that the physical presence of teachers allows for immediate access to clear explanations and guidance. This minimizes confusion and ensures that learners can easily grasp complex concepts. The ability to seek clarification in real-time fosters a sense of confidence and a more relaxed learning experience.

Okwuduba et al. (2022) indicated in their study that various forms of learning support, such as teacher, peer, and parent support, along with different dimensions of learner engagement, including emotional, behavioral, cognitive, and adaptive factors, were positively correlated with the achievement of learners in science. The study has relevance for both preservice and in-service teacher education, particularly in terms of instructing instructors on how to actively cooperate with parents in motivating their children to become involved and accomplished academically.

Structured Learning. In a traditional classroom setting, the educational process is often well-organized and follows a logical sequence. This structured approach to learning facilitates a deeper understanding of the subject matter and enhances the overall educational experience. This was reflected in the recollections of FL1:

*Sa klasrum man gud sir kay naay ginasunod nga class program, lahi lahi ginaklase namu sa isa ka adlaw mao nga dili mi maboring ug naa pud mi klasmeyts dili parehas sauna tong sa balay lang ko, nagastudy lang ko, ako lang isa, ug ginakapoy ko...
(Lines 38-41)*

...Tong nagamodule pa mi sauna, wala may teacher, ginalaktawan lang naku tong lessons

nga di naku ganahan ug di naku masabtan. Pero karon nga naa nay teacher, ang mga lessons or topics kay pasunod naman maong dili naku kapili or kalaktaw laktaw sa lessons maong mas makaanswer naku sa mga pangutana...(Lines 78-82)

...Ug kung ang teacher magpaanswer sa amoa ug activity, tapos iyaha dayon tsekan. Unya inig human niyag tsek, iexplain dayon niya kung asa mi nagkamali, mao nang masabtan namu ang lesson, kung asa mi tama o mali... (Lines 117-120)

(In the classroom, sir, there is a class program being followed; we have different subjects tackled in a day that makes us not bored since we also have classmates with us, not like before at home, where I studied on my own, and I felt exhausted.

During the time that we are using self-learning modules (SLM), there is no teacher, and I do skip some topics or lessons that I don't like and don't understand. But now that there is a teacher, the lessons or topics are sequenced or have a sequence to follow, so I cannot skip lessons, which is why I can now answer questions better.

The teacher gave us an activity to answer, and checked it right away. After checking, the teacher will explain to us where we answered wrong; that is why we understand the lesson better, whether we got it right or wrong.)

The recollections of the learner clearly revealed the one of the advantages of easy and sequenced learning in a face-to-face environment, which has a clear progression from one topic to another. Teachers can systematically build upon previously covered material, ensuring that learners have a solid foundation before moving on to more complex concepts. This gradual and structured approach allowed learners to grasp each topic thoroughly, reducing the risk of confusion or gaps in their knowledge.

Additionally, sequenced learning frequently corresponds with the logical order that the curriculum brings, making it simpler for learners to make connections and see the bigger picture. This methodical approach to learning not only enhances comprehension but also fosters a sense of confidence among learners. They felt more in control of their education, knowing that they can follow a logical path to mastering the subject matter.

Structured learning, as defined by Smith (2023), is a methodical and deliberate approach to learning. Predetermined learning objectives, content, delivery methods, and evaluation procedures are all part of structured learning, designed to achieve specific learning outcomes. It provides a methodical and organized approach to learning, which can improve the efficiency, efficacy, and relevance of the learning process. Nevertheless, it also poses specific difficulties that necessitate meticulous strategizing, execution, and assessment.

Indeed, the easy and sequenced learning is a key attribute of face-to-face instruction that control group learners appreciate. This structured approach to education ensures that learners can progress through the curriculum methodically, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter and a greater sense of confidence in their learning journey.

Clear Explanations. The clarity of explanations provided by teachers in the context of face-to-face instruction is a significant advantage valued by learners, particularly those in

control group. The availability of teachers for questions and clarifications in a physical classroom setting greatly enhances the comprehension of complex topics and contributes to the overall effectiveness of the learning process.

In a traditional classroom, teachers have the unique ability to offer immediate and clear explanations. When learners encounter challenging concepts or have questions, they can seek guidance and receive answers in real time. This direct interaction ensures that any misunderstandings are addressed promptly, allowing learners to stay on track with the curriculum and avoid falling behind. This is evident in the recollections shared by all participants:

FL2: *Ganahan ko sa face-to-face kay nakatuon kog tarong. Sa face-to-face, kung dili mi makasabot, iexplain pa sa teacher ug tarong ang lessons. Kung dili ko kasabot, maghangyo lang ko sa teacher nga utruhon pag-explain. Kung wala gyud ko kasabot, makadiretso kog pangutana sa teacher nga kamao mo explain sa lesson sa akoo. Ug matubag gyud ko ug dali-dali sa amoang teacher. (Lines 176-181)*

(I like face-to-face because I learn better. In face-to-face instruction, if we cannot understand, the teacher further explains the lessons. If I cannot understand, I request that the teacher repeat the explanation. If I do not understand, I can directly ask my teacher, who is able to explain the lessons to me. And the teacher can immediately answer me.)

FL3: *...Karon man gud nga pagtuon sir makapangutana ko diretso sa amoang teacher, ug sa akoang mga klasmeys. Ug mas nakasabot ko ug tarong kay naa may makatudlo sa akoo kung maglibog ko. (Lines 272-275)*

(Sir, in studying, now I can directly ask my teacher and also my classmates. I learned better because there is someone teaching; I will not be confused.)

FL1: *Sa face-to-face, lipay kaayo ko. Nalipay ko kay naay teacher nga naga explain...kung gusto pa naku ug daghan pa nga example, makahatag dayon ang among teacher. Mao na ang hinungdan nganong ganahan ko. (Lines 32-36)*

Importante gyud kayo ang teacher kay siya man ang gahatag ug explanation. Kapoy kayo sauna tong naga module lang mi...pero karon dili na kapoy. Mas nakabalo nami pag-ayo, kung asa ang isulat o asa ang i-take note. (Lines 60-64)

Ang among teacher, maexplain kaayo niya kung unsa ang naa sa LAS, unya gahatag pud ug daghan examples para masabtan gyud namu ug tarong. Tong dili kasabot ug English, ginatranslate...ni teacher para masabtan sa mga estudyante. (Lines 111-114)

(In face-to-face, I am very happy. I am happy because the teacher can explain... If I like more examples, the teacher can give them easily. That is why I like it.

The teacher is very important since he or she is the one giving the explanation. It is so exhausting during modular instruction, but now

(face-to-face) not exhausting anymore. We now know better what part of it to write or take note of.

The teacher will explain well what is in the LAS, then give more examples for us to understand clearly. To those who cannot understand English, the teacher will translate it for them so that the students will understand.)

The learners showed enthusiasm toward learning, knowing that teachers were present in their academic journey. Teachers often develop a deep understanding of the individual

learning styles of their learners and can tailor their explanations to suit the needs of the class. Customizing teaching methods ensures that learners can access complex topics more easily, leading to improved comprehension. Learners in control group have appreciated the immediate support provided by teachers, which enhances their understanding of complex topics and contributes to their academic success.

Learners who participated in the class reported that the interactive educational exercises enhanced the lesson contents, enabled them to assess their comprehension of important content areas, and influenced their choice about attending in-person classes. Learners discovered that attending class was more beneficial than studying the course materials on their own, even while class recordings were available. Those who opted out of the class did not experience firsthand the benefits of the interactive learning approach (Lewohl, 2023).

Supportive Environment. The classroom environment in face-to-face instruction often serves as a supportive and secure space for control group learners. This setting encourages learners to express their opinions, ask questions, and seek help with ease. The sense of security and support in the classroom plays an important role in strengthening the confidence of learners in their educational journey. The physical classroom offers learners a space where they can freely express their thoughts and opinions. The presence of peers and teachers creates an atmosphere where open discussions are encouraged, and diverse perspectives are valued. The narrations of all participants showed this:

FL1: *...Ang akong mga kasamang guro ug akong guro, sir, kay ginangnan ko nila nga dili mag ulaw-ulaw, nga mag apil gyud ko kung naa mi ginahimu sa klase kay wala may mag katawa o magsuko kung maka answer ko ug mali. Maong ganahan ko diri sa skul kay kabalo ko nga makapangutana ra ko kay naa man koy pasensiyoso ug hilabihan magsuporta nga teacher ug klasmeyts who nagatabang sa paggiya naku ug kauban naku sa pagtuon. Ginaingnan pud mi sa amoang teacher nga magtinabangay para mas makatuon pa gyud mi. (Lines 120-128)*

(My classmates and my teacher, sir, encourage me to not be shy and instead participate in our activities because no one will ever laugh or scold me if I answer wrong. So, I love being at school knowing that I can ask questions without hesitation because I have patient and supportive teachers and classmates who will be my guide and companion in my studies. We were encouraged by our teacher to help one another in order to learn better.)

FL3: *...Ginaingnan mi pirme sa amoang teacher nga dapat tabangan amoa klasmeyt o katapad nga wala nakasabot sa lesson. Ang amoang teacher sir, pirme gyud niya ginaparamdam sa amoa nga okay ra gyud kaayo nga mangutana mi labi na ug wala mi nakasabot, ginaingon gyud niya nga matubag gyud niya dayon kung naa mi mga pangutan-on, mao nang dili na ko maulaw mangutana sa klase. (Lines 284-290)*

(Our teacher will always tell us to help our classmates or seatmates who do not understand the lesson. The teacher, sir, always lets us feel secure enough to ask questions if we do not understand, assuring us that we will immediately be given answers to our questions. That is why I am not ashamed to ask questions in class.)

FL2: *...Mas ganahan naku karon magbasa ug mag-answer. Ganahan naku mag-apil sa mga ginahimu sa klase tungod kay ang amoang teacher dili man masuko kung mali ang akoang ma-answer. Ginaingnan pud mi niya ug ang akoang mga klasmeyts nga dili mi magkatawa o dili bullyhon ang makaanswer ug mali, dapat tabangan daw ug tudluan para makaanswer sila ua tama. (Lines 226-231)*

(I now like to read and answer. I like to participate in class because my teacher did not scold me if I answered wrong. The teacher also told us, my classmates, not to laugh or bully anyone who answered wrong; instead, help them and teach them in order to come up with the right answer.)

Learners expressed a feeling of being more comfortable participating in classroom discussions and sharing their viewpoints, having the presence of teachers and peers who will not criticize them but instead help them when they answered wrong, which fosters critical thinking and social skills.

The classroom environment fosters a safe space for learners to seek help, fostering confidence and motivation. It encourages open expression, encourages discussions, and provides accessible support, enhancing the effectiveness of traditional instruction and its enduring appeal. This supportive environment contributes to the overall educational journey.

The research conducted by Monteiro et al. (2021) showed that children who thought their educators used constructive criticism more effectively also showed higher levels of school identity and engagement with behaviors. Even after accounting for the influence of individual judgments and efficient criticism of instructors, we still saw the impact of a supportive classroom environment on learner involvement. Despite varying opinions on teacher feedback, students exhibited elevated levels of school identification and behavioral engagement in classes where educators employed more effective feedback strategies to cultivate a supportive classroom environment.

Improved Focus and Comprehension. Face-to-face instruction highlights the improved focus and comprehension as a crucial advantage of this traditional approach. Learners in control group often find that the absence of distractions commonly associated with distance learning environments allows them to concentrate fully on the subject matter, resulting in better comprehension and retention of the material.

One of the key advantages of face-to-face instruction is the conducive atmosphere for learning that a physical classroom offers. The absence of digital distractions, such as social media notifications or the lure of other online activities, enables learners to maintain their focus on the lesson at hand. This undivided attention is instrumental in deepening their understanding of the subject matter, as they can engage with the material without interruptions. As some of the participants stated:

FL1:...Okay na akong pag-eskwela karon, sir, kay masabtan na naku ang mga lesson sa face-to-face kaysa atong nagamodule lang mi. Sa face-to-face, lipay ko, nalipay ko kay ginaexplain ug tarong sa teacher ang amoang lesson. (Lines 13-16)

...Mas nakasabot naku sa lesson karon tungod kay inig human namu basa sa LAS gina-explain man dayon ni teacher. Ug nagahatag pa gyud si teacher ug daghan nga example. (Lines 51-53)

...Mas maka-pokus naku karon, kay kung nay direction o instruction sa LAS nga dili naku nasabtan, mai-explain pa man ug tarong sa teacher. Mao nang maka-answer ko, maka-answer mi ug tarong sa mga pangutana didto sa LAS. (Lines 82-86)

(My studies are okay since I can understand the lesson face-to-face rather than in mere modules. In face-to-face, I am happy. I am happy because the teacher can explain the lesson well.

I better understand the lesson because, after we read the LAS, the teacher explains it. Then the teacher can give more examples.

I am more focused now, because if there are directions (instructions) in Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) that I cannot understand, the teacher will further explain them. That is why I or we can better answer those questions in LAS.)

FL3: Sa face-to-face, mas nakatuon ko ug daghan kay nasabtan naman naku ang lessons, kay kung malisudan ko ug sabot, makapangutana man ko diretso sa amoang teacher... (Lines 300-302)

(In face-to-face, I learned even more because I understood the lessons, because if ever I find it hard to understand, I can ask my teacher directly.)

The physical presence of teachers and classmates in the classroom provided an assurance of focused learning away from distractions, which fosters accountability, encourages active participation, and improves comprehension. The absence of digital distractions and the distraction-free environment enhance the effectiveness and enduring appeal of traditional in-person education, thereby improving the learning experience.

One of the elements that affects how well learning is implemented is students' focus on what they are learning. Conversely, insufficient attention from students can lead to a lack of success in meeting learning objectives. The study's findings demonstrated the validity, reliability, and normal distribution of the learning and learning achievement data. If the student is truly attentive, they will effectively adhere to and execute the learning tasks. The level of attention a student exhibits in class not only affects their participation but also has a significant impact on their learning outcomes. When students are able to concentrate effectively during a lesson, they are more likely to comprehend and successfully address all the questions related to the learning materials. This, in turn, leads to higher scores and greater learning achievements. On the other hand, those who paid less attention in class might struggle to understand the subsequent learning materials, which could cause them to fall behind and possibly feel overwhelmed and unhappy during the course (Hariyanto, 2021).

Sense of Community

The Sense of Community theme explores into the intangible yet powerful aspect of traditional education, creating a strong sense of community. In a face-to-face classroom, learners experienced a feeling of togetherness, developed a unique bond with their teachers, and engaged in cooperative and teamwork activities. This theme underscores the social and emotional aspects of education, exploring how they foster a supportive and nurturing environment where learners can thrive in the face-to-face instructional context.

Pei et al. (2023) revealed the key components that seemed useful in contributing to a sense of community: collaborative educational endeavors within schoolwork, informal and outside-of-school engagements spanning various subjects, and the educational

institution functioning as a tangible environment that integrates educational and social facets of life in a post-COVID. The learners also noted two problems: first, despite how much they valued group projects, they found it challenging to control group dynamics; second, they believed that teachers held the last position of authority in the learning process, which led to conflict in the teacher-learner relationship.

Community Feeling. The core idea Community Feeling in face-to-face instruction is a testament to the unique and powerful sense of togetherness that learners in control group experienced in a traditional classroom setting. This sense of community arises from the shared physical space, the common goal of learning, and the interactions that occur among learners and teachers. As all of the participants shared:

FL1:...*Ganahan ko magtuon sa eskwelahan, sir, kay naay teacher, mga klasmeys, ug mga amigo sa face-to-face. Dili parehas sauna katong nagatuon lang ko sa balay, kay isa lang ko, bation ko ug ka boring, mingaw, ug ginakapoy ko. Matabangan nami sa amoang pagtuon kay naa naman amoang teacher nga nay dakong kahibalo. (Lines 41-46)*

(I like studying in school, sir, because we have a teacher and classmates and friends in face-to-face. Unlike before, studying at home, I was alone; I got bored, lonely, and exhausted. We can now get help in our studies having the presence of our teacher, who is an expert in giving information.)

FL2:...*Diri sa skul kay dili boring kay daghan ug mga bata, mga klasmeys. Nagadula mi...nagasulat mi. Dili siya boring kay daghan ug mga bata ug mga klasmeys. Makapangutana pud ko sa ilaha kung naa koy wala nasabtan para mas makatuon. (Lines 184-188)*

(In school, I do not feel bored because there are lots of kids, my classmates. We play...we write. It is not boring because there are lots of learners/kids and classmates. I can ask my classmates if I ever do not understand some of the lessons, so I can learn better.)

FL3:...*Karon sir, sa skul, lipay kaayo kay naa akong mga friends, mga klasmeys, ug teachers. Ganahan ko magtuon sa skul karon kay lingaw kay nagadula-dula mi, naa koy baon ug mapalit naku akoang gusto na merienda ug mabusog ko. (Lines 294-297)*

(Now that I am in school, I am happy; I have my friends, classmates, and teachers. I do love to learn in school now because it is fun since we can play there, I have my baon and I can buy my favorite merienda and be full.)

The shared physical space in a classroom fosters a sense of community among learners, allowing them to establish routines and bond with their surroundings. The shared goal of learning has united them, reinforcing their sense of belonging to the learning community. This collective endeavor motivates students to work together and support one another.

According to a study by Kałuzna-Wielobob (2017), as cited in Kałuzna-Wielobob et al., (2020), community feeling pertained to the intrinsic connection between an individual and other people, encompassing a sense of solidarity or detachment from others. Individuals with a strong sense of community drive a desire to promote collective well-being, while those with a weak sense of community seek to assert their superiority over others as a means of compensating for their internal feelings of inadequacy. The findings indicated that individuals with stronger communal sentiments exhibit reduced levels of anxiety, elevated self-esteem, and enhanced psychological well-being compared to those with weaker communal sentiments. This demonstrates that those with high self-esteem exhibit

more resilience throughout task performance and maintain their drive even in the face of failure.

Teacher-Learner Bond. The teacher-learner bond is a fundamental aspect of face-to-face instruction that holds deep significance for control group learners. The direct, in-person interaction between teachers and learners in a traditional classroom setting often leads to the development of a wholesome and lasting connection. This bond extends beyond the classroom and can evolve into mentorship relationships that have a significant impact on the personal and academic development of learners.

The personal interactions that occur in a physical classroom create an environment where teachers and learners can get to know each other on a deeper level. This connection often goes beyond the formal roles of instructor and learner, as teachers come to understand the individual strengths, weaknesses, and interests of their learners. This deeper understanding allows teachers to tailor their guidance and support to the specific needs of each learner, fostering a sense of trust and personal connection. As all of the participants narrated that:

FL2: *Nagapaminaw ko sa akoang teacher, kung gusto niya magsulat mi kay magsulat pud ko... (Lines 197-198)*

...Gusto naku magbasa ug mag-answer sa lessons namu kay kabalo naku nga nay magtudlo ug mag guide sa amoa. Dali rapud ko matubag sa akoa teacher kung naa koy pangutan-on. (Lines 208-210)

(I am listening to my teacher; if what he wants us to write, I write also.)

I like to read and answer lessons since there is someone teaching and guiding us. The teacher can easily answer me if I have questions.)

FL3: *...Naa akong mga klasmeyts ug teachers nga makatudlo ug kauban sap ag-eskwela maong dali ra ko makasabot... (Lines 257-259)*

(My classmates and teachers are there who will teach and my companion in studying, so I easily understand.)

FL1: *Sa klasrum, kung ginakapoy nami, ginapahimu napud mi ug nindot na activity ni teacher, ginakwentuhan mi ug kwento nga makapaganahan sa amoa nga magstudy gyud ug tarong para maabot namu ang amoang mga pangarap, ug tungod ani mas makapokus nami sa pagpaminaw. (Lines 66-70)*

(In the classroom, if ever we get tired, our teacher presents other engaging activities and tells us stories that inspire us to study hard in order to achieve our dreams someday; this really caught our attention and made us listen attentively.)

Many learners found that their relationships with teachers served as a source of mentorship and guidance throughout their academic journey. These mentors offer valuable advice, support, and encouragement, helping learners navigate challenges, set goals, and reach their full potential. These relationships can have a lasting impact, shaping not only the academic success of learners but also their personal and professional development.

Moreover, Soldaat (2019) found that the emotional dedication of teachers to their work leads to job satisfaction and strengthens the foundation for establishing strong bonds with

learners. These bonds are influenced by socio-cultural, moral, professional, physical, and political closeness. Physical and emotional distance between teachers and learners may lead to a lack of understanding, resulting in a negative classroom atmosphere. To improve the efficacy of these linkages and foster emotional comprehension, teachers should assume distinct roles, such as coach, counselor, and parental figure. This fosters emotional comprehension, strengthens connections, mitigates emotional detachment, and enhances classroom interactions. The attitude of teachers towards teaching and the academic success of learners are largely influenced by the establishment of strong bonds with learners. Nurturing these relationships over time leads to a more profound and intimate connection, resulting in beneficial outcomes for the educational process.

The personal interactions in the classroom often lead to deep connections and mentorship relationships that profoundly influence the personal and academic growth of learners. This bond underscores the invaluable role of teachers in the lives of control group learners, creating a supportive and nurturing educational environment.

Cooperation and Teamwork. Cooperation and teamwork are fundamental aspects of face-to-face instruction that provide control group learners with valuable opportunities to develop essential interpersonal skills. In a traditional classroom setting, learners engage in group works and collaborative activities, which contribute to their overall personal and academic development. As all of the participants recollected:

FL1: *...Ginatabangan...namu amoang klasmeyts kung dili sili makasabot. Gina explain pud naku sa ilaha kung paunsa naku naansweran o paano naku nakuha ang answer. Habang nagalesson mi, pwede magtinabangay sa pag-answer. (Lines 141-144)*
(We help our classmates if they cannot understand. I will explain to them how I answered or how I got the answer. While having lectures, we can help other classmates learn how to answer.)

FL2: *...Usahay nagapangutana ko sa akoang katapad para tudluan o eksplanan ko sa amoa lesson, ug nakatuon gyud ko tungod ana. (Lines 191-193)*
(Sometimes, I ask my seatmate to teach (or explain) the lessons to me, and I also learn from that.)

FL3: *...Tungod kay naay mga klasmeyts ug mga teacher nga makatudlo sa amoa ug sa akoo, maong mas dali lang mi, dali lang ko makatuon sa mga leksiyon. (Lines 302-305)*
(Because my classmates and teachers are there to teach me and my classmates, it becomes easier for us to understand the lessons.)

Learners felt that through the availability of cooperation and teamwork in the classroom, they had the confidence to learn the lessons effectively. Group works in the classroom fosters effective communication, problem-solving skills, and practical skills. It encourages learners to exchange ideas, share responsibilities, and delegate tasks, enhancing their understanding of the subject matter. The ability to collaborate effectively is a sought-after skill in the professional world, and the experiences gained in face-to-face instruction prepare them for success in a wide range of personal and professional endeavors.

It is really evident that collaborative activities promote social interaction among learners and encourage the exchange of ideas and perspectives. Through teamwork, learners

develop essential interpersonal skills such as communication, leadership, and conflict resolution, which are essential in both academic and work settings. In the end, by embracing cooperation and teamwork, face-to-face instruction nurtures a sense of community and mutual support, reinforcing the overall educational experience.

The study conducted by Kristiansen et al. (2019) revealed that learners and their interpersonal behavior, their engagement and active involvement in the cooperative learning (CL) process, communication and assistance towards one another, and the influence of teachers in fostering learner interaction are crucial factors for achieving successful CL in small groups. Furthermore, these elements can contribute to the profound acquisition of knowledge by the pupils. Nevertheless, research indicates that in order for the CL approach to achieve success, it is important for educators as well as learners to engage in carefully planned procedures.

Experiences of the Experimental Group Learners about the Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction

Perceived Value of RBI

The theme of the perceived value of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) highlights the capacity of RBI as a tool for consolidating knowledge which enable learners to engage with lessons at their own pace and reinforcing their understanding as manifested in the core ideas: reviewing lessons, value in the absence of teacher, and replay for better understanding.

RBI, as a valuable resource for reviewing lessons, allows learners to revisit content at their own pace, consolidating knowledge and promoting self-assessment. It also serves as a substitute for traditional face-to-face instruction when teachers are away, ensuring uninterrupted learning. The adaptability and empowerment provided by the RBI enable learners to pursue their education autonomously, promoting self-reliance and a sense of progress. It also provides a powerful tool for replaying lessons, enhancing comprehension, and engaging more deeply with the subject matter. This feature encourages deep learning and continuous exploration by fostering a sense of autonomy and flexibility.

Yayen and Marensil (2021) concluded that both learners and parents really understand the exceptional effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly in the context of responsiveness and learning feedback, quality of learning instruction, time allotment, availability and capability, and awareness and preparedness. They both believed that it was a useful learning tool that might help schoolchildren learn even in the absence of in-person instruction.

Reviewing Lessons. Learners found plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) useful for reviewing lessons. This core idea emphasizes a fundamental dimension of RBI's impact on learners' educational journeys. Throughout the data, learners consistently expressed the value they place on RBI as a means to revisit and reinforce previously covered content. The convenience and accessibility of RBI provided learners with a

powerful tool for review, allowing them to navigate their educational materials at their own pace. This review process is not merely a cursory glance at past lessons; it is a structured means of self-assessment, a way to consolidate their understanding, and a method to dive deeper into complex subject matter.

RBI essentially functions as a versatile repository of knowledge, enabling learners to return to instructional materials whenever they need to refresh their memory, clarify doubts, or solidify their grasp of the curriculum. This kind of flexibility aligns seamlessly with the modern preferences of learners for self-directed and independent learning, giving them the autonomy to navigate their education at a rhythm that suits them. Whether it is a challenging topic or a quick refresher before an assessment, learners find RBI to be a dependable companion, supporting them in their quest to revisit and engage with the curriculum at their convenience. The ability to review lessons is not just a supplemental aspect of their learning process; it is a dynamic and integral part of their ongoing educational journey. As RL1 narrated:

Sa RBI, sir, kay mura ra kag nagareview. Kung naa mi assignments, mareview ra namu ang amoang lessons kung amoang i-play ug balik ang recorded lessons. Kay maulit man gud sir ang amoang lesson, kay makareview pa mi sa balay sir kung nay RBI. (Lines 339-342)

(In RBI, sir, it seems that you are reviewing. If we have an assignment, we can review our lesson by playing the audio-recorded lessons again. Our lessons can be repeated; we can review lessons even when we are at home because of RBI.)

The learner here revealed that the act of reviewing lessons through RBI surpasses the traditional limitations of time and place. RBI, as a technology-assisted learning tool, allows learners to engage with their curriculum anytime and anywhere, transforming traditional learning boundaries. This unrestricted access allows learners to have a sense of control and empowers them to plan their own path of learning, highlighting the transformative power of technology-assisted learning.

It was aligned with the study of Asis and Bayani (2023), who found that television and radio-based education were beneficial for learners as these technologies provide additional explanations and enhance the technological skills of learners. This convenient method allows learners to review past conversations at their discretion, especially when they struggle with understanding lessons. It enables them to comprehend information at a quicker pace and enhance their understanding of the lessons. Despite initial unfamiliarity, the approach yields positive outcomes by improving technological proficiency.

Value in the Absence of Teacher. The core idea that plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) is considered valuable, especially when there is no teacher present, sheds light on the pivotal role RBI plays in educational experiences of learners, particularly in scenarios where traditional face-to-face instruction is temporarily unavailable. Through their testimonies, learners emphasize that RBI serves as a reliable and versatile educational tool that steps into the role of an instructor when teachers are absent due to various reasons, such as seminars or other important events. This underscores the adaptability and the crucial role that the RBI plays in ensuring that the learning process

remains uninterrupted. As some of the participants declared:

RL1: *Nakatabang ang RBI sir, kay kung halimbawa sir kay kung wala man guy teacher sir, di ba nagface-to-face na ta? Kung wala man guy teacher sir kay kung naa gud silay kuan ah adtoan sir...oh, seminar kay hatagan lang mig module (LAS) ana sir sa Math tas hatagan pud mi atong gikuan sa lesson, girecord sa USB...kay para makuan namu to maansweran namu tong dili masabtan sa among gibasa ug gipaminawan. Kung wala amoang teacher sir, dali gihapon mi makasabot kay amoa ra man i-play ang lesson didtoa sa RBI. (Lines 367-374)*

(RBI is useful, sir, like when there is no teacher... because they go somewhere to attend important events like seminars, they will just give us modules or LAS in Math and audio recorded lessons in USB to let us answer those we do not understand in what we read while listening. In the absence of a teacher, we can still easily understand because we can play the lessons on RBI.)

RL2: *...Kanang kani ang nagpuli ug tudlo sa amoa, sir, labi na tong walay teacher nga magtudlo sa amoa. Hangtod karon sir, nga naa nay face-to-face, naay panahon nga magseminar amoang teacher, matabangan mi sa amoang pagtuon pinaagi sa audio-recorded lessons nga ginahatag sa amoa. (RL2, Lines 524-528)*

(It replaces the facilitation of learning, sir, in times when there were no teachers teaching us. Until now that we already have face-to-face learning, in times like when teachers have attended seminars, the audio recorded lessons have helped us learn.)

It was reflected that in situations where learners might otherwise be left without instruction, RBI emerges as a dependable resource, offering access to educational content and guidance. It serves as a lifeline, allowing learners to continue their educational journey without reliance on the physical presence of a teacher. This dimension of the perceived value of RBI highlights its role in fostering learner independence. It instills a sense of agency among learners, enabling them to progress in their studies even when educators are momentarily unavailable. In essence, RBI becomes an empowering educational tool, promoting self-directed learning, and ensuring that the absence of a teacher does not hinder the educational progress of the learners.

The findings of Jaime-Osorio et al. (2019) highlighted the significant correlation between the recording, broadcasting, and reflection on a program on the radio and the enhancement of the oral proficiency of learners, their motivation to learn, the advancement of discussion, and the fostering of learner coexistence. Establishing an English-language radio broadcast is a significant substitute for foreign language instruction. The enhancement of the oral communication abilities of learners was apparent throughout the procedure. Notably, learners demonstrated substantial progress in speaking examinations, despite the absence of English language teachers before the commencement of the initiative. Nevertheless, the absence did not influence the effect of the radio program on the English language-speaking abilities of the learners.

Replay for Better Understanding. Learners accounted for their experiences in the replay feature of RBI as a powerful tool that significantly enhanced their comprehension of educational content. It allows learners to revisit and engage with specific parts or the entirety of a lesson, providing them with the flexibility to navigate the curriculum at their own pace. As all of the participants recollected:

RL1...*Sa RBI kay pwede pa namu maulit ang mga lessons. Nakatabang nig dako sa akoo sir kay kung unsa ang gina explain tanan to mao ang nakasulat sa LAS ug maulit-ulit pa namu ug play kung gusto namu. Usahay sir, kaduha o katulo naku ulit-uliton ug play ang audio-recorded lessons kay para mas masabtan gyud naku. Pwede pa nimu ma ulit-ulit ug play ang mga lessons hangtod makasabot. (Lines 358-364)*

(In RBI, we can replay the lessons. It contributes a lot because what is being explained is all there inside the LAS and we can still play it again if we want to. Sometimes I play the audio-recorded lessons twice or sometimes three times until I understand them. You can play the lessons again and again until you understand.)

RL2: *Sa RBI kay pwede pa nimu maulit ug play ang mga lesson para mas makatuon gyud ug tarong. (Lines 511-512)*

(In RBI, you can still replay the lessons for better learning.)

RL3: *Sa RBI sir, iyong mga lesson ay pwede siya ulit-ulitin. (Lines 618-619)*

(In RBI, sir, you can replay the recorded lessons.)

Learners shared that they found a means to deepen their understanding of educational material through the replayability feature of RBI. The ability to revisit sections or the entire lesson until it aligns with their level of comprehension offers an invaluable opportunity for self-directed learning and self-assessment. This dimension of RBI fosters a profound engagement with the subject matter, allowing learners to fine-tune their understanding and learning experiences.

In fact, Khadija (2020) revealed that university learners have a strong connection with technology. Still, learners favor educational radio broadcasts on two Fez radio stations, specifically Radio SNRT and Radio Plus. The data indicated that learners see radio educational broadcasts as a supplementary tool for learning rather than a complete replacement for in-person instruction. These broadcasts had a significant favorable influence on the progress of learners during the COVID-19 lockdown. Regarding the difficulties learners face, most of them are resolved by the presence of audio materials on the platform of the faculty. Learners can replay these materials at their convenience, allowing them to acquire knowledge at their own pace.

Replayability feature of RBI is a valuable tool for learners as it allows them to navigate complex topics, revisit challenging sections, and clarify doubts. It reduces the pressure of the real-time classroom environment and helps learners fully internalize educational content. RBI, through its replay feature, addresses this issue by providing learners with the agency to revisit, revise, and fully internalize educational content. This improvement is in line with modern educational approaches, accommodating various learning preferences and optimizing educational results.

Flexibility and Accessibility

The theme of flexibility and accessibility within the context of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) captures the dynamic and transformative nature of this technology-assisted learning platform. Insights into how the flexibility and accessibility of RBI have become cornerstones of their educational experiences are revealed through the accounts of the learners. It is reflected through the core ideas: convenience of access, access from anywhere, and replacing classroom facilitation.

Radio is a portable and affordable alternative to television for learning, providing offline lessons without internet data. It is beneficial for those without devices or internet access, especially those residing in rural areas. Radio courses offer both students and parents the opportunity to listen to audio lessons, facilitating learning and understanding complex subjects. The audio and sound effects are clear and captivate the audience, effectively conveying the subject matter. The presentations are skillfully delivered, making radio an excellent alternative to online education. Radio courses provide numerous alternatives for learners to study and answer module questions in the comfort of their homes, led by parents and elders. The learning experience is similar to in-person instruction, with the teacher providing detailed explanations (Potane, 2022).

RBI, as a form of blended learning, is a modern education approach that allows learners to choose when and how to engage with their educational content, allowing them to adapt to their pace and preferences. This flexibility is a distinguishing feature of modern education, surpassing the rigid schedules of traditional classrooms. The RBI guarantees the accessibility of educational opportunities to a broader audience, regardless of geographic or infrastructural limitations. Additionally, it serves as an accessible lifeline during times of teacher absence or when there are interruptions in conventional in-person teaching. The transformative power of RBI in contemporary education is evident in its ability to empower learners to take charge of their educational experiences, ensuring that educational resources are accessible to all, regardless of traditional constraints.

Convenience of Access. In today's educational landscape, accessibility to educational materials has raised concerns for everyone. The widespread adoption of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) has brought forth a paradigm shift, offering learners unprecedented convenience of access to educational resources. The accounts of learners revealed the significant impact of RBI accessibility on their educational outcomes. As RL1 recounted:

Kuan sir, baski wala signal gikan sa estasyon sa radyo, sir, pwede ra gihapon namu mapaminawan ang girecord na lesson nga gibutang sa USB. Pwede ra namu maullit-ulit ug play ang lessons baski kanus-a namu gusto, amoa lang ibutang sa radyo nga gihatag sa eskwelahan para maplay na ang lessons nga paminawan. Habang gapaminaw pud sir, sundan lang naku ug basa ang nakasulat sa LAS nga mao pud ang ginaestorya sa teacher nga nagatudlo sa recorded lesson para makasabot... (Lines 344-351)

(Even if there is no radio frequency signal, we can still listen to the recorded lessons saved on a USB flash drive. We can play the lessons repeatedly whenever we want to; we just plug it into the radio distributed to us from school to play the lessons and we can listen to it. While listening, I will just follow what was written in the LAS, which is also the same as what is being broadcast by the teacher in the recorded lesson for me to understand.)

The learner consistently expressed the appreciation for the convenience of accessing RBI lessons. This convenience refers to the ease with which learners can engage with educational content on their own terms. The digital nature of RBI allows for a seamless integration into the life of the modern learner. Whether it is reviewing lessons, catching up on challenging topics, or simply exploring new subject matter, RBI offers learners the flexibility to learn when it suits them best. This adaptability extends beyond traditional classroom hours, allowing learners to engage with their educational materials at their convenience.

Radio has been significant in the realm of education since its inception. The radio technology has made significant advancements throughout the decades. However, the fundamental premise has remained unchanged: to connect with a large number of people at a reduced expense. The immediacy, accessibility, and simplicity of the media possess the necessary resources to maintain its significance in the educational system during times of crisis. The enduring influence of radio as a means of communication can be attributed to its ability to transmit messages over long distances, thanks to its extensive coverage and widespread availability. Due to its cost-effectiveness and independence from energy, it possesses the capacity to reach extensive audiences. Hence, it is considered the most readily available technological tool for the spread of knowledge. Research has indicated that radio is the predominant broadcast medium employed for educational purposes during periods of emergency globally. This is attributed to its affordability and convenient availability (Okeke et al., 2020).

The convenience of access provided by RBI is not limited to specific settings or scenarios. It aligns with the preferences and needs of modern learners who seek an education that adapts to their pace and lifestyle. This core idea highlights the transformative potential of technology-assisted learning platforms like RBI, which offer a dynamic and accessible approach to education. It underscores the shift towards a more learner-centered and inclusive model of learning, ensuring that educational resources are available to learners, regardless of traditional constraints.

Access from Anywhere. The core idea reflects the remarkable flexibility and accessibility that this technology provides to learners. The narratives of learners emphasized the significance of RBI in allowing them to engage with educational content, even when they are physically distant from their devices. As some of the participants reiterated:

RL1: *Kanang makuan pud nimu siya sir, kanang madunggan gyud nimu siya sir baskin layo ka sa gadget o radyo. Pwede nimu madala ang radyo baski asa ka mag-ado kay gamay ug gaan ra man siya. (RL2, Lines 517-519)*

(You can still listen to the lessons even if you are far from the gadget or radio. You can carry the radio transistor wherever you go since it is small and not heavy.)

RL3: *...Sa RBI sir, kasi may radyo man, pwede mo pa rin siya mapakinggan kahit saan ka. Pwede mo rin siya mapakinggan kahit nasa bahay ka lang. (Lines 619-621)*

(In RBI, because there is radio, you can listen to the lessons anywhere. You can also listen to it even at home.)

The ability of RBI to grant access from anywhere is a fundamental aspect of its design. It permits learners to surpass physical limitations, enabling them to engage with their educational materials regardless of their location. Whether they are at home, on the move, or in remote areas with limited access to traditional classroom resources, RBI remains within reach. This dimension of access aligns with the need of the modern learner for education that is not tied to a specific place but is available whenever and wherever they wish.

The importance of access from anywhere becomes particularly evident when learners are a little bit far from their gadgets. This aspect underscores the resilience of RBI in ensuring uninterrupted learning. Even when learners are busy and quite far from their devices, they

can still access and engage with their educational content by just listening to the played audio-recorded lessons. This adaptability offers a sense of continuity and flexibility that is highly valued by the learners. It reinforces the idea that technology-assisted learning platforms like RBI can serve as catalysts for ensuring that educational resources are not constrained by proximity to the learning materials.

In their study, Prahmana et al. (2021) emphasized the establishment of an alternative learning model that utilizes sophisticated technology to facilitate remote learning in areas that are geographically far and face educational limitations. In distant places, the only technology that can be accessible remotely is radio communications. Therefore, implementing blended learning utilizing technology was prioritized to address the educational requirements. This learning approach combines in-person and remote learning through the utilization of technology. Blended learning is the optimal learning approach for combining distance learning with radio network technology in rural locations. It embodies the fundamental concepts of alternative education in distant regions, employing radio networks within the framework of community radio advancement.

Replacing Classroom Facilitation. This core idea highlights the transformative role that plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) plays in filling the void left by the absence of teachers in traditional classrooms. The accounts of learners illustrate the invaluable contribution of RBI when educators are temporarily unavailable. This is reflected in the recollections of some participants:

RL1:...*Kung wala man guy teacher sir kay kung naa gud silay kuan ah adtoan sir...oh, seminar kay hatagan lang mig module (LAS) ana sir sa Math tas hatagan pud mi atong gikuan sa lesson, girecord sa USB...kato na ang magtudlo sa amoa kay para makuan namu to maansweran namu tong dili masabtan sa among gibasa ug gipaminawan. Kung wala amoang teacher sir, dali gihapon mi makasabot kay amoa ra man i-play ang lesson didtoa sa RBI kato naman ang magtudlo sa amoa... (Lines 380-387)*

(When there is no teacher...because they go somewhere to attend important events like seminars, they will just give us modules (LAS) in Math and audio-recorded lessons on USB. It is now the one teaching us in order for us to answer those we do not understand in what we read while listening. In the absence of a teacher, we can still easily understand because we can play the lessons in RBI and it is the one teaching us)

RL2:...*Kanang kani ang nagpuli ug tudlo sa amoa, sir, labi na tong walay teacher nga magtudlo sa amoa. Hangtod karon sir, nga naa nay face-to-face, naay panahon nga magseminar amoang teacher, matabangan mi sa amoang pagtuon pinaagi sa audio-recorded lessons nga ginahatag sa amoa.(Lines 524-528)*

(It replaces the facilitation of learning in times when there were no teachers teaching us. Until now, when we already have face-to-face learning, in times like when teachers have attended seminars, the audio-recorded lessons have helped us learn.)

RBI, as learners attested, steps into the role of an instructor when teachers are absent due to seminars, important events, or other reasons. It became a reliable substitute for traditional face-to-face classroom instruction, ensuring that the learning process remains uninterrupted. Learners perceived RBI as a versatile and empowering educational tool, allowing them to continue their educational journey without reliance on the physical presence of a teacher. According to Ablir (2022), teachers have embraced and valued the implementation of radio-based instruction, primarily employing it as a supplemental form

of distance learning to educate learners who are unable to attend in-person sessions or reside in remote areas. These were helpful lessons for achieving the goals that the teachers had established.

This dimension of the role of RBI in replacing classroom facilitation underscores its adaptability to diverse educational settings. The consensus among learners regarding the significance of RBI in the absence of teachers strengthens the versatility and effectiveness of technology-assisted learning platforms in ensuring that education remains accessible, even when educators are momentarily unavailable.

Benefits of Audio Instruction

This theme explores into the positive impact of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) on the educational experiences of learners. The theme emphasizes the supremacy of technology-assisted learning platform like RBI to provide an inclusive, accessible, and enriching educational experience for learners as revealed in the core ideas: less exhausting for readers, enhancing understanding, beneficial for non-readers, and listening anywhere. The testimonies of learners highlight the multifaceted advantages that audio-based instruction provides in the context of their learning journey.

Potane (2022) accentuated the benefits of radio to individuals lacking a device or internet access. Parents, as well as learners, could listen to the audio lessons. It facilitates the process of acquiring knowledge and allows individuals to understand complex subjects that may be challenging for them to comprehend. The music and sound effects are clear and captivating, conveying the subject matter effectively and delivering the presentations skillfully. Providing learners with the chance to listen to the course through radio can enhance their understanding, particularly for those students who lack access to television.

Likewise, Garba (2020) noted that along with ease of access, proximity, involvement, and steady program flow, most respondents said that community-based radio stations provided greater benefits to them.

Less Exhausting for Readers. This core idea reflects the awareness of learners to the significant advantages that audio instruction offers, particularly for individuals who engage with extensive reading. The testimonies of the learners highlight the importance of this aspect in their educational experiences. As all of the participants narrated:

RL1: ...Ako lang ginapaminawan ang audio-recorded lesson kung unsa ang ginatudlo habang akoang ginagunitan ug ginasundan ang naa sa LAS ug para maansweran ang mga pangutana nga gusto nila paansweran sa amoa. (Lines 351-354)

(I will just listen to the audio-recorded lessons while holding the Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) to follow along and answer the questions.)

RL2: Katong time nga naga RBI na, nagapaminaw lang ko para makatuon sa mga lessons. (Lines 487-488)

(The time that there is RBI, I just listened to it to learn the lessons.)

RL3: Ang pinakanagustuhan ko sa RBI ay siya ang nagabasa para sa iyo kaya hindi na masyadong mapagod ang mga bata na magbasa. Nakikinig na lang ako...sinusundan ko lang ang LAS... (Lines 613-615)

(The first thing I like about RBI is that it is the one reading for you, making it not exhausting for the learners to read. What I did was just listen...and follow the LAS.)

Audio instruction, as perceived by learners, provides a pleasant break from the demands of extensive reading. They expressed their appreciation for the relief that audio-based content offers, especially when dealing with voluminous or complex subject matter. This dimension of audio instruction addresses the issue of reading fatigue, which can often be a barrier to effective learning. Learners find audio instruction to be a valuable alternative to traditional text-based materials, offering a more accessible and less exhausting approach to engaging with educational content.

Wright (2024) defined burnout as a mental, physical, and emotional exhaustion experienced by children with learning and thinking differences. Academic challenges, supplementary instruction, and psychological issues contribute to increased stress and frustration. Societal expectations, intense relationships, and lack of peer connection also contribute to the heightened susceptibility of school burnout. Raisanen et al. (2020) mentioned that study-related exhaustion can lead to difficulty in learning new information, as learners who felt more worn out from studying had more trouble picking up new information in class.

The core idea emphasizes the inclusive nature of audio instruction as it accommodates the diverse learning preferences and abilities of individuals. Learners who may struggle with prolonged reading or those seeking to optimize their learning experiences find audio instruction as a valuable supplement. It promotes a more inclusive learning environment, making educational content accessible to a broader range of learners with varying abilities and preferences. It alleviates the fatigue associated with extensive reading, promoting a more inclusive and accessible learning experience.

Enhancing Understanding. This core idea explores the transformative impact of audio-based explanations on learners' comprehension of complex topics. The narratives of the learners emphasize the significance of this dimension in their educational experiences. As some participants shared:

RL1:...*Sa RBI, ang lesson sa 1 week kay gihimu ra ug 30 minutes to 1 hour lang human na dayon dili parehas sa face-to-face nga kadaghan. Didto, ginahatagan nami ug instruction kung unsaon pag-answer sa lesson didto sa LAS nga bisan lisod ang lesson pero masabtan gihapon namu pagmaminaw mi sa explanation kay ginahatag naman gud didto sir ang mga instructions kung paunsa answeran ang activity. Mas dali masabtan kay gamay naman lang among paminawan na discussion. (Lines 406-413)*

(In RBI, a week lesson was reduced to 30 minutes to 1 hour of audio recorded lessons, unlike in face-to-face, which is more. There, we are well instructed on how to answer the lessons in our LAS, so even if it is a difficult lesson, we can still understand after we listen to the explanations because the instructions on how to answer the activity were given there. We can easily learn because of the lessened time of discussion that we will listen to.)

RL3:...*Kung minsan, kung hindi mo maintindihan ang lesson, mas napapadali pa rin ang pag-aaral kasi ito naman ang nag-eexplain ng lesson sa iyo tungkol sa nakasulat na lesson sa LAS... (Lines 615-618)*

(Sometimes, if you cannot understand the lesson, it still helps foster learning because it is the one who explains the lesson written on the LAS.)

Learners consistently expressed the view that audio explanations play an important role in helping them understand complex topics. Complex topics for a weekly lesson budget were reduced to a 30-minute to 1-hour lesson presentation that is both simpler and more comprehensive. The direct-to-the point lesson presentation enables learners to grasp complex concepts more effectively, providing a level of clarity and depth that is often challenging to achieve through text-based materials alone.

In effect, audio instruction, with its focus on in-depth explanations, becomes a powerful tool for learners seeking a comprehensive understanding of educational content. Learners appreciate that audio instruction provides them with a more accessible and engaging approach to learning complex subjects. This enhances their motivation and encourages deeper engagement with the curriculum, ultimately leading to improved comprehension. Potane (2022) highlighted the effectiveness of audio teaching in facilitating learning by helping learners understand challenging concepts. The use of clear music and sound effects skillfully delivered by audio teachers can be particularly beneficial for students without television access.

Beneficial for Non-Readers. The use of audio-based instructional materials is viewed as a key component, especially when students are facing literacy obstacles. This emphasizes the inclusive nature of this educational resource and its benefits for non-readers. In educational environments, there exist various types of learners. Some learners require additional stimulation, while others need supplementary academic assistance, and some may benefit from using technology to aid them in acquiring everyday skills. Technology enables children with disabilities to access speech-to-text applications. This allows those who excel at expressing their thoughts verbally to enhance their writing and speaking abilities. Integrating technology during station time will enable students to receive intervention or engage in more advanced activities (Ablir, 2022). The testimonies of the learners emphasized the crucial role that audio instruction plays in providing access to educational materials for non-readers. As RL3 reiterated:

Makatulong man din ito, sir, lalong-lao na sa hindi makabasa kay ito man ang nagabasa at naga-explain ng lesssons para sa kanila. Kasi kung hindi sila marunong magbasa, patugtugin lang nila ang lesson at pakinggan nila ito para matuto pa rin sila... (Lines 625-628)

(It is beneficial to non-readers, for it is the one who reads and explains the lessons for them. If ever they don't know how to read, they just play the lesson and listen to it for them to still learn.)

The learner shared the emerging value of audio instruction as a bridge to educational content for those learners who may struggle with reading or literacy. By delivering spoken explanations and instructions, audio instruction ensures that non-readers can access and engage with the curriculum. This inclusive approach promotes equal opportunities for all learners, regardless of their reading abilities. It empowers non-readers to participate fully in the educational process, fostering a sense of inclusivity and engagement.

Moreover, audio instruction recognizes that the diversity of learners includes those who may have different learning styles and abilities. Audio instruction caters to a broader audience, ensuring that educational resources are not limited by traditional constraints. Learners who may have faced barriers in traditional text-based educational settings find

audio instruction to be an enabling and accessible alternative. This core idea underlines the power of technology-assisted learning platforms like plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) to provide a more equitable and inclusive educational experience for learners of diverse backgrounds and abilities. In essence, audio instruction acts as a catalyst for breaking down barriers to learning and promoting a more inclusive, equitable, and accessible educational environment.

Listening Anywhere. One of the main advantages of plug and play radio-based instruction is that it allows learners to access and listen to the instructional content from anywhere, regardless of their location. This provides convenience and empowers learners. The recollections of learners emphasized the significance of this dimension in their educational experiences. As some participants described:

RL2: *Kanang makuan pud nimu siya sir, kanang madunggan gyud nimu siya sir baskin layo ka sa gadget o radyo. Pwede nimu madala ang radyo baski asa ka mag-adto kay gamay ug gaan ra man gud siya. (Lines 517-519)*

(You can still listen to the lessons even if you are far from the gadget or radio. You can carry the radio transistor wherever you go since it is small and not heavy.)

RL3: *...Sa RBI sir, kasi may radyo man, pwede mo pa rin siya mapakinggan kahit saan ka. Pwede mo rin siya mapakinggan kahit nasa bahay ka lang at pwede mo pa siya maulit-ulit na pakinggan. (Lines 628-631)*

(In RBI, because there is radio, you can listen to the lessons anywhere. You can also listen to it even at home, and you can listen to it again and again.)

Learners consistently acknowledged the convenience of listening to lessons from anywhere. Audio instruction aligns with the dynamic lifestyle of the modern learner and the need for education that is not confined to a specific location. It is accessible whether at home, on the move, or in remote areas with limited connectivity. Whether at home, on the move, or in remote areas with limited connectivity, audio instruction ensures that educational content is always within reach, even without access to traditional classroom resources.

Miao et al. (2020) also revealed traditional radio as a popular educational method that caters to students regardless of their geographical location. It is accessible through most radio channels and relies on the ability of the brain to concentrate on auditory information. This remote learning mode is suitable for many countries, as they own public, private, and community radio stations, making it an ideal choice for ongoing education.

The ability to listen to lessons from anywhere is particularly valuable when traditional classroom settings may be disrupted or when educators are temporarily absent. Audio instruction, through its portable and accessible nature, becomes a lifeline that ensures uninterrupted learning. Learners can engage with their educational content at their convenience, making learning an adaptable and flexible process that accommodates their unique circumstances and needs.

Comparing Face-to-face and RBI

When learners start using plug and play radio-based instruction, they frequently analyze its similarities and differences compared to face-to-face instruction and may indicate a

preference for the latter. Within this theme, the learners' recollections provided useful insights into the intricate ways in which these two modes of education influence their learning experiences.

The study of Baba and Ojakovo (2021) identified several obstacles to effective teaching of listening comprehension in senior secondary schools. The factors found to have influenced listening comprehension include the subject matter of the text, the clarity of the voice of the teacher, the quality of the audio materials, the type of audio materials used, the length of the listening text, the method of oral assessment, the method of written evaluation, the use of questioning as a teaching strategy, the language used in the listening text, and the incorporation of visual aids, real-life objects, audio materials, and teaching methods. The study also revealed a significant difference in listening comprehension skills between students taught using audio materials and those exposed to classroom text, affecting literal understanding, inference-making, and critical thinking.

Learners compared face-to-face instruction and technology-assisted learning (RBI) in traditional classroom settings in terms of perceived differences, effectiveness comparisons, concerns about cheating, and note-taking. Face-to-face instruction is praised for its immediate teacher-student interaction, while RBI is valued for its flexibility, accessibility, and the ability to revisit lessons at a personal pace. These comparisons provide a comprehensive understanding of the strengths and limitations of each educational mode, contributing to a broader understanding of the evolving landscape of education in an era of educational innovation and transformation.

Effectiveness Comparison. The core idea encapsulates the complex dynamics of the perceptions of learners regarding the effectiveness of the two educational modes. The testimonies of the learners revealed the diversity of views and opinions on which mode, face-to-face teaching or plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI), they consider more effective for their learning. It is evident in the testimonies of some participants:

RL2:...Kung naa man gud teacher sir, makaanswer ka sa mga pangutana sa atubangan niya. Mabalik balik pud sa teacher iyahang mga examples nga ginahatag. Sa face-to-face kay masabtan gyud nimu ang lesson ug masabtan pud nimu unsa ang i-answer. Sa radyo, makasabot man pud pero ang uban kay pwede makakopya kay usahay ginaingon man gud sa ulahi sa lectures ang mga answer. (Lines 468-473)

(If there is a teacher, you can answer the questions in front of him. The teacher can repeat the examples given. In face-to-face, you can really understand the lesson, and you can understand what the answer will be. While on the radio, the learners have a chance to cheat because sometimes answers are given at the end of the lectures.)

RL3:...Nakatulong man din ang RBI sir pero konti lang. Ang masasabi ko lang, may naitulong man din ito sa pag-aaral kasi noong wala pang face-to-face, ang RBI man ang ginamit para maipagpatuloy at para matulungan kami para maintindihan ang mga lesson. (Lines 592-595)

(RBI just helped a little. I can say that it has still contributed to learning since, when there is no face-to-face instruction, RBI is the one used to help in understanding the lesson.)

The accounts of learners indicated a range of perspectives. Some learners expressed a preference for face-to-face teaching, emphasizing the benefits of immediate teacher-student interaction, real-time clarifications, and the social aspects of the

classroom. They find that this mode is particularly effective for certain aspects of their learning journey. Conversely, other learners acknowledged the value of the RBI. They highlighted its flexibility, accessibility, and the ability to revisit lessons as key factors that contribute to their learning experience. For these learners, RBI represents an effective alternative that aligns with their preferences and needs.

Kenter (2023) revealed that students who received instruction with audio assistance outperformed those who received instruction using the traditional way of teaching. The study confirmed learners acquired listening comprehension abilities more rapidly and effectively when audio aids were employed in instruction, as opposed to when they were not utilized. Audio aids mitigate the primary drawback of relying solely on verbal communication by the teacher, offer a captivating method to introduce a new subject and establish accurate initial perceptions for the learners.

Additionally, Rosete and Nool (2022) revealed that learners face various challenges when using RBI as a teaching tool, including individual, institutional, technological, and household barriers. Learners employed strategies like online alternatives, improving their technical proficiency, and fostering a desire to learn. RBI offers educational benefits like improved understanding, increased motivation, collaborative interaction, convenience, and cost-effectiveness. However, learners also identify limitations such as intellectual limitations, time allocation, study assistance, expenses, and technology issues. Despite these challenges, learners believe RBI has positively impacted their schoolwork.

This core idea reflects the learner-centered nature of modern education, where the effectiveness of educational modes is perceived and evaluated through the lens of individual preferences and needs. It underlines the adaptability of the educational process to cater to a wide range of individual preferences. The effectiveness comparison provides insights into the nuanced and multifaceted nature of education, where different learners may find different modes of instruction more effective for their specific learning goals.

Concerns about Cheating. As learners engage with plug and play radio-based instruction, a notable concern arises regarding the potential for cheating in the absence of direct oversight by teachers, prompting reflections on the integrity of the learning process in a technology-assisted learning environment. Their accounts shed light on the complexities and challenges associated with maintaining academic integrity in technology-assisted learning environments. As RL2 attested:

Sa face-to-face sir, kay masabtan gyud nimu ang lesson ug masabtan pud nimu unsa ang i-answer. Sa radyo, makasabot man pud pero ang uban kay pwede makakopya kay usahay ginaingon man gud sa ulahi sa lectures ang mga answer. Ang uban pud sir kay nagapaanswer sila sa uban para daghan silag maanswer nga tama... (Lines 463-467)
(In face-to-face you can really understand the lesson and what the answer is. On the radio, learners can cheat by taking advantage of answers that are sometimes provided at the end of the lectures. Also, other learners seek the help of others to answer in order to have many correct answers.)

The learner expressed concerns about the possibility of cheating when using RBI. This concern arose from the asynchronous nature of RBI, where learners have access to educational content independently, often outside the direct supervision of teachers. The

learner recognized that this autonomy may create opportunities for academic dishonesty, such as copying answers from external sources or receiving unauthorized assistance during assessments.

Further, Aguilar (2021) identified several key factors that contribute to learners engaging in academic dishonesty. These factors include an overwhelming workload due to poor time management skills, a lack of ability to study independently due to a limited understanding of lessons and inadequate guidance from parents and educators, indolence, societal influence, and the demand for exceptional academic performance.

Moreover, Villaruz et al. (2022) emphasized the challenge of maintaining the standard and honesty of education in a remote or hybrid learning environment. The study unveiled the viewpoints of STEM students regarding blended learning and homeschooling. Blended learning incorporates the participation of parents and other family members as learning guides as long as the teachers, parents, and learners agree on the limitations to ensure that the learning maintains quality and integrity. Parents, teacher, and student must reach a consensus on the optimal approach to ensure the integrity and quality of education provided in homeschooling.

The concern about cheating reflects a broader conversation about the evolving landscape of education and the need to balance the advantages of technology-assisted learning platforms with measures to ensure academic integrity. It underscores the importance of establishing clear guidelines and ethical standards in the use of RBI in the digital age to maintain the credibility and fairness of the educational process.

Taking Notes. The significance of note-taking in studies is undeniable, serving as a fundamental practice for learners to synthesize information and enhance their understanding. It allows them to actively engage with the content, reinforce retention, and facilitate later review and comprehension. In this core idea, learners recognized the opportunity to take notes during plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) and appreciated the value it added to their learning experience. As RL2 shared:

...Akong ginahimu sir kay akong utruhon ug paminaw sa balay, mga kaduha o katulo lang para makakuan pud ka sir maka take note, mura ka ug nagastudy. Kay sa skul baya sir kuan paspas kaayo ug usahay dili naku makopya tanan na ginapakopya. Nakadungag siya sa akoa gana magtuon kay pwede ka pa magsulat o magtake note para kung halimbawa nalowbat tong radyo, pwede pud ka makasunod didto sa imong gisulat sa notbuk nimu. (Lines 477-483)

(What I did was repeatedly listen to the lessons at home, twice or three times for me to take down notes; it seems that I am studying. In school, I cannot take down all the notes that needed to be copied because it is fast-paced. It does increase my interest in studying because you can write or take down notes so that if the radio gets low on battery, you can still follow your lessons in your notes.)

The learner consistently highlighted the ability to take notes as a significant advantage of RBI. In contrast to face-to-face instruction, where note-taking can be limited by the pace of the class and the availability of materials, RBI, along with learning activity sheets (LAS), provides learners with the flexibility to jot down key points, questions, and insights as they listen to the audio content while following the printed LAS. This note-taking ability enables

learners to personalize their learning experience, allowing them to capture important information and engage with the material in a more active and reflective manner.

DepEd Sarangani (2021) addressed challenges related to the high reproduction costs of printing self-learning modules by introducing a shift to learning activity sheets (LAS) for K–12 learners in the second quarter of the academic year 2020–2021. This change, accompanied by plug and play radio-based instruction and other learning resources, aimed to streamline presentation and enhance content retention. The LAS includes basic information, the concept digest, and activities, with each topic or competency condensed to 1-2 pages. This approach seeks to alleviate issues such as learner exhaustion from reading lots of papers, material shortages, internet connectivity issues, gadget scarcity, and radio signal problems. The provision of LAS, along with plug and play radio-based instruction, allows learners to take note of only the gist of the lessons at their own pace without being pressured by the time.

Moreover, the capacity to take notes during RBI also served as a tool for self-assessment and revision. Learners can review their notes at their convenience, reinforcing their understanding of the content and facilitating the retention of information. It empowers them to engage with the educational content on their own terms, contributing to a more comprehensive and effective learning process.

Challenges and Criticisms of RBI

There are several perspectives of learners on the difficulties and criticisms associated with plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI). Their testimonies provide insights into the multi-dimensional aspects of using technology-assisted learning platforms and the potential issues learners encounter during their educational journey.

In the theme, the researchers came up with three core ideas: dissatisfaction with RBI, critique of instruction speed, and reluctance to answer questions. Learners shared their experiences and concerns about the challenges and criticisms they face when engaging with RBI. These may include issues related to access, technical difficulties, concerns about academic integrity, or the perceived limitations of technology-assisted instruction.

Through their testimonies, learners highlighted the need for addressing these challenges and criticisms to ensure that RBI is an effective and equitable mode of education. This theme offers valuable insights into the complexities of integrating technology into the learning process and the importance of adapting educational platforms to meet the diverse needs and preferences of learners.

Khadija (2020) indicated that students, primarily millennials and centennials with an inseparable connection with technology, have exhibited positive attitudes towards educational radio. Nevertheless, they embrace radio classes, considering it an obsolete distance education. Students perceived radio educational broadcasts as a supplementary tool for learning rather than a direct replacement for in-person instruction, which significantly influences the learning outcomes of students during the COVID-19 lockdown.

While students occasionally encountered difficulties comprehending the audio materials, they demonstrated enthusiasm for this remote education mode. Given the implementation of instructional radio broadcasts as an alternative educational approach amidst this crisis, it is apparent that students may have challenges effectively comprehending and absorbing the content of the radio courses.

Dissatisfaction with RBI. The dissatisfaction of the learners with the adoption of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) was illuminated by this core idea. There could be various reasons why learners may not favor plug and play RBI. Their accounts revealed that some learners find RBI less meaningful or effective for their educational needs and preferences. As some of the participants revealed:

RL3: *...Kung papipiliin ako sir, ayaw ko nalang mag RBI, mas maganda pa rin kasi ang face-to-face kay maexplain pa ng teacher. Sa RBI kay walang teacher na pwedeng mag-explain sir kung paano gawin ang module kung may dagdag pa ako na itanong. Kung minsan kasi may maintindihan man ako sa ginalesson sa (RBI) audio-recorded lessons pero minsan din hindi ko maintindihan ang lesson. Kung magbalik naman ang pandemic na hindi na talaga pwede magface-to-face na klase at RBI lang talaga ang paraan para makapag-aral, tanggapin ko nalang siguro sir kay wala naman akong choice. (Lines 575-584)*

(If I will be given a chance to choose, I don't like RBI, face to face is even more meaningful or even better because there is a teacher who explains. In RBI, there is no teacher present to further explain how to do the module if ever I have other questions to ask. Sometimes I understand the lessons through the audio recorded lessons, but sometimes I do not understand them either. If ever situations like the pandemic return wherein face-to-face classes are prohibited and RBI is the only mode of learning, then maybe I can accept it because I don't have a choice.)

RL2: *Ginasunod lang naku tong ginaestorya sa radyo, sir, pero dili gyud kaayo naku nasabtan ang lesson. Lahi ra gyud tong face-to-face nga nay nagatudlo nga teacher kay mas masabtan gyud. Kay kung naa man gud koy wala nasabtan sa lesson maderetso man gud nimu ug pangutana, sir, tapos matubag pud ka dayon sa teacher maong mas masabtan. (Lines 500-505)*

(I was just following what was being discussed on the radio, yet I did not understand the lessons well. Face-to-face is far different, where there is the presence of a teacher who can teach and make the lessons easy to understand. If ever I do not understand the lesson, I can directly ask the teacher, and the teacher can give me real-time assistance, which is why I can learn better.)

Learners expressed their dissatisfaction with RBI by highlighting aspects of this mode of instruction that do not align with their expectations or experiences. These criticisms may range from perceived limitations in content delivery to concerns about engagement levels, direct or real-time discussions and assistance, clarity of explanations, or the overall effectiveness of RBI.

The findings of the study of Maphosa (2021) showed that teachers favored using computers, laptops, and smartphones over radios while instructing students. Likewise, Ayanwale et al. (2023) noted that learners have had varying experiences, with specific individuals finding radio and television captivating while others encounter difficulties with participation and flexibility. The findings pointed out that while most participants recognized the efficacy of radio and television as educational tools, they expressed the

view that the instructional content lacks sufficient depth. Moreover, educational television broadcasts are more advantageous than radio courses due to the substantial contribution of visual stimuli to the learning process.

The core idea underscores the importance of acknowledging and addressing learner concerns to enhance the quality and relevance of technology-assisted learning platforms like RBI. It served as a reminder that, while technology can offer innovative and adaptable solutions for education, it must continually evolve to meet the diverse needs and preferences of learners. Understanding and addressing dissatisfaction with RBI is essential for optimizing the learning experience and ensuring that education remains a meaningful and relevant endeavor. It emphasized the need for evaluation to implement improvement and adaptation to create more effective and satisfying learning experiences for all learners.

Critique of Instruction Speed. The core idea of Critique of Instruction Speed within the theme of Challenges and Criticisms of RBI reflects the pace at which audio recorded instructions are delivered in plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) as critiqued by the learners. As RL3 expressed:

...Ang nagbabasa kasi ng instruction sa audio-recorded lesson sir kay minsan nagabasa ng mabilis, kung minsan din ay mabagal magbasa. Pero pinapakinggan ko na lang para masundan ko ang lesson sa LAS. (Lines 600-603)

(The one who is reading the instruction (in an audio recorded lesson) sometimes reads so fast, and some read so slowly. But then, I still listen in order to follow the lessons in LAS.)

The learner expressed concerns about the speed of instruction in RBI, noting that some audio-recorded lessons are delivered too quickly while others may be too slow. This variation in pace can pose challenges for comprehension and engagement, especially when the learners are striving to follow complex or unfamiliar topics. The critique of instruction speed by the learners emphasized the importance of clear and effective communication in the learning process.

Lange and Costley (2020) identified five primary categories of commonly occurring media delivery issues. These categories include pace, intelligibility, quality, media diversity, and congruence. Because of these concerns, improper media usage can impede knowledge acquisition. In the context of visual media, pace refers to the speed of information delivery. This speed has an impact on how learners interact with the content and absorb information. The following terms for pace include: speed, fast, faster, slow, slower, quick, rate, and time. Intelligibility refers to the learner's ability to accurately perceive and hear media-delivered content, allowing them to make sense of the information.

The core idea highlights the significance of addressing issues related to instruction speed in technology-assisted learning platforms. It underscores the need for flexibility in content delivery to accommodate learners with diverse learning styles and levels of familiarity with the subject matter. Providing options for adjusting the pace of instruction can enhance the accessibility and effectiveness of RBI, ensuring that all learners can engage with the content at their own speed and comprehension level.

Reluctance to Answer Questions. Learners' reluctance to answer questions highlights the apprehension and hesitation of the learners in responding to questions or assessments within the context of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI). The learners' perception of limited autonomy and choice in their educational experiences often drives this reluctance. As RL3 mentioned:

Nakatulong man din ang RBI, sir, kaso konti lang, mag answer na lang ako sa mga tinatanong sa LAS sir kay no choice man...para lang makapasa sa subject... (Lines 598-600)

(Yes, RBI has helped me, but just a little. I reluctantly answer the questions that follow since I have no choice but to answer just to pass the subject.)

The learner expressed his reluctance to answer questions in RBI due to a sense of constraint. The learner may feel compelled to answer questions because he perceives that he has no other alternative. This sense of obligation can diminish the intrinsic motivation to engage with the content and assessments fully.

The recollections of the participants regarding academic procrastination are intriguing discoveries derived from their firsthand experiences, exploring both the underlying causes and the resulting outcomes. Overall, the pandemic led learners to procrastinate due to restricted access to instructor guidance, technology assistance, and increased distractions in their home environments. The perspectives of the participants on the impact of academic procrastination can vary, either positively or negatively, according to how the circumstances are handled (Adona et al., 2021).

Jadaone et al. (2022) mentioned the coping mechanisms students used in blended learning to deal with the challenges they encounter in this new mode of education, as well as their opinions on how well-prepared they feel for higher education. Students acknowledged that they do not have a choice but to endure and embrace the difficulties of blended learning and devise strategies to manage it, such as engaging in learning on their own. They believe that independent learning will equip them with the necessary skills to prepare for college.

The core idea underscores the importance of learner agency and autonomy in education. It points to the need for creating learning environments that empower learners to make choices and engage with assessments willingly. Addressing this reluctance requires designing RBI and similar technology-assisted learning platforms in a way that fosters learner motivation and engagement. It highlights the need for evaluation to implement improvement and adaptation to enhance learner engagement and satisfaction with technology-assisted education.

Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Summary Table of Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Findings of the Control Group on the Effects of Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction on the Performance of Grade V Learners in Mathematics

Table 11 shows the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings of the significant difference in the mean scores of the control group in pre-test and posttest performance in mathematics which provide valuable insights on the effectiveness of the use of face-to-face instruction on the performance of Grade V learners. The quantitative data reveal a significant difference in mean scores between the pretest and posttest for the control group engaged in face-to-face instruction. The mean score increased from 7.00 in the pre-test to 11.53 in the posttest, suggesting a noteworthy improvement in performance. This statistical difference accentuates the effectiveness of face-to-face instruction in enhancing the academic outcomes of learners in mathematics.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative data in this study provides a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of face-to-face instruction. The qualitative data highlight the incomparable edge of face-to-face instruction as a traditional method that provides a holistic learning experience, fostering academic knowledge, critical social and emotional skills, and a sense of connection with educators through hands-on activities, experiments, and collaborative work, deepening comprehension and problem-solving abilities. The findings align with the quantitative data, emphasizing the unmatched value of face-to-face learning in improving the academic performance of learners.

The incomparable implication of this integration showed the capacity of face-to-face instruction to improve academic performance in the digital age, which lies in the unique interpersonal and collaborative aspects it offers. Face-to-face instruction stands out amidst the dominance of digital learning platforms due to its ability to foster immediate and personal interactions. The qualitative data presented emphasizes the significance of collaborative learning, instant feedback, and peer support in a face-to-face setting. These elements contribute to a rich and dynamic learning environment that may be challenging to replicate in purely digital formats. While digital tools offer convenience and accessibility, face-to-face instruction, with its emphasis on real-time interaction, remains incomparable in its potential to enhance the academic performance of learners in the evolving landscape of education.

In conclusion, the combination of quantitative and qualitative data not only confirms the effectiveness of face-to-face instruction but also enriches our understanding of the factors contributing to this success. The findings suggest that the interactive and collaborative nature of face-to-face learning fosters a positive learning environment, ultimately leading to improved academic performance.

Summary Table of Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Findings of the Experimental Group on the Effects of Plug and Play Radio-based Instruction on the Performance of Grade V Learners in Mathematics

Table 12 shows the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings of the significant difference in the mean scores of the experimental group in pre-test and posttest performance in mathematics which provide valuable insights on the effectiveness of the use of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) on the performance of Grade V learners. The quantitative data reveal a significant difference in mean scores between the pre-test and posttest for the experimental group engaged in plug and play RBI. The mean score increased from 7.13 in the pre-test to 12.53 in the posttest, signifying a remarkable improvement in performance. This statistical difference highlights the effectiveness of the instructional approach in enhancing the academic outcomes of learners in mathematics.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative data in this study provides a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of plug and play radio-based instruction in improving the academic performance of learners. The qualitative data highlight the flexibility and adaptability of the technology, emphasizing its effectiveness in facilitating learning even in the absence of a physical teacher. The data also show the preference of some learners for face-to-face instruction, despite the positive impact of RBI, which underscores the importance of considering diverse learning preferences and the role of teacher-learner interaction. The findings align with the quantitative data, which revealed RBI to have a tangible and positive impact on the academic performance of learners.

The implication of the integration of both qualitative and quantitative findings suggests that while plug and play RBI contributes significantly to academic performance and offers flexibility, a balanced approach that considers the preferences of learners and maintains the value of traditional teaching methods may be crucial for a comprehensive and effective educational strategy. Integrating the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative aspects can inform further refinements to optimize the impact of plug and play RBI on learning outcomes.

To fully harness the potential of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) and significantly improve the performance of learners, the adoption of a multifaceted approach is needed. This involves comprehensive teacher training and ongoing professional development to ensure effective utilization of RBI, seamless integration of the technology with the curriculum, and the creation of engaging, interactive content aligned with the needs of the learners. A feedback mechanism, continuous monitoring, and evaluation are crucial for refining RBI content and methods. Additionally, fostering community engagement, exploring sustainable funding models, and promoting research and innovation contribute to the long-term success of plug and play RBI, making it a transformative tool for education.

In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the efficacy of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) through the lens of the RAT model (Replacement Amplification Transformation Model). First, the recognition of learner preferences for face-to-face

instruction emphasizes the replacement aspect of the RAT model, in which technology replaces existing instructional approaches without altering them. The significant enhancement in mean scores aligns with the amplification aspect of the model, demonstrating how technology, in this case, RBI, can improve academic performance and foster engaging learning experiences. Finally, the qualitative insights illuminate the adaptability and convenience of the RBI approach, particularly in scenarios where physical teacher presence is limited, showcasing the transformational potential of technology in reshaping teaching and learning practices. As a result, moving forward, further development and refinement of technology, alongside a comprehensive approach that blends traditional and innovative instructional methods, can facilitate holistic and effective learning experiences for Grade V learners in mathematics.

Conclusions

In the light of the research's findings, the subsequent conclusions are therefore offered:

1. Learners in the control group (which in face-to-face instruction) generally perform poor in the pre-test.
2. Learners in the experimental group (which in plug and play radio-based instruction) generally perform poor in the pre-test.
3. There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of the experimental group (which in plug and play radio-based instruction) and the control group (which in face-to-face instruction).
4. Learners in the control group (which in face-to-face instruction) performed fair in the posttest.
5. Learners in the experimental group (which in plug and play radio-based instruction) showed little or moderate improvement or fair performance in the posttest.
6. There is no significant difference in the performance of learners in mathematics with the use of face-to-face instruction alone compared to the performance with the use of face-to-face instruction with the aid of plug and play radio-based instruction.
7. There is a significant improvement in the performance of the learners between the pre-test and posttest mean scores of the control group (which in face-to-face instruction).
8. There is a significant difference between pre-test and posttest mean scores of the experimental group (which in plug and play radio-based instruction).
9. Learners in the control group, which is in face-to-face instruction, were provided with unique and holistic learning experiences. The physical classroom environment fosters interaction and engagement, learning support, and a sense of community among learners. Through social interaction, hands-on activities, and teacher and peer support, learners develop critical, social and emotional skills. Face-to-face instruction allows for immediate feedback and the development of a personal rapport between educators and learners, which is invaluable for their academic growth. It also helps instill a sense of discipline, time management, and responsibility. Face-to-face instruction was beneficial for students as it provided them with a structured, engaging and supportive learning environment.
10. Learners in the experimental group, which is in plug and play radio-based instruction,

have experienced a flexible and accessible learning platform with various benefits, such as consolidating knowledge, providing an inclusive, accessible, enriching educational experience, and enhancing understanding. While it has its drawbacks, such as audio quality issues and limited access to materials, the advantages of this technology-assisted learning platform outweigh the challenges and criticisms. Thus, plug and play radio-based instruction is an invaluable tool for providing students with a dynamic and transformative learning experience.

11. The adoption of plug and play radio-based instruction (RBI) was found to have a minimal impact on the performance of learners in mathematics. Learners in their shared descriptions of experiences revealed a preference for face-to-face instruction while expressing reluctance to learn in lessons using plug and play radio-based instruction due to some undermining factors such as the capacity of learners to learn on their own, the style of teachers in delivering audio-recorded lessons, and other aspects. The findings pointed out the difficulties encountered when adopting plug and play RBI, emphasizing the significance of direct teacher-learner interaction for effective learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Drawing from the aforementioned findings and conclusions, a series of recommendations may be put forth:

1. In order to foster an inclusive and effective educational environment, the Department of Education may prioritize the integration of inclusive educational technologies. The department may promote the integration of plug and play radio-based instruction technologies in the educational system to address different learning needs and achieve positive outcomes. This approach aligns with the commitment of the department to providing equitable and accessible educational opportunities for all learners.
2. To enhance the educational experience within schools, administrators may prioritize investment in technology resources. Allocating resources to address issues such as audio quality and material accessibility in technology-assisted learning may contribute to the overall improvement of the learning environment. This strategic allocation of resources aligns with the goal of providing learners with a technologically enriched and effective educational experience.
3. Teachers have a crucial impact on shaping the learning experience. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers incorporate interactive strategies in in-person teaching. Incorporating engaging and participatory strategies may create improved learners' engagement and strengthen personal ties with the learners, as seen by the positive experiences described by the control group. This approach is consistent with the goal of establishing a dynamic and supportive learning atmosphere within the classroom.
4. Parents are key stakeholders in the education of the child, and their support is essential. Recognizing the benefits of both face-to-face instruction and technology-assisted learning, parents may actively communicate with educators to understand and enhance the educational experiences of their children. Thus, parents' active involvement in their children's education may have led to the development of

well-rounded and adaptable learners.

5. For learners, responsible use of technology is paramount. It is recommended that learners make good use of technology, leveraging the flexibility and accessibility of plug and play radio-based instruction while being conscious of its limitations. Through the responsible utilization of technology, learners may maximize the benefits of dynamic learning experiences, contributing to a more effective and personalized learning journey.
6. Continued exploration is essential for refining educational practices. The researchers are encouraged to further investigate the factors that contribute to the significant disparity in posttest scores between the control and experimental groups. Conducting further research may provide valuable insights into areas for improvement and contribute to the continuous enhancement of educational methodologies.
7. In order to further develop the current understanding, it is recommended that other researchers replicate and expand on the study. Exploring different contexts and variables may contribute to the validation of findings and a deeper understanding of effective teaching methodologies. This collaborative and repetitive study approach may strengthen the foundation of educational research and provide guidance on future studies.
8. In order to establish flexible and captivating learning settings, educational institutions are encouraged to promote blended learning policies. Advocating for the integration of face-to-face instruction and technology-assisted learning may enable institutions to harness the strengths of both methods, providing students with a comprehensive and versatile educational experience.
9. Policy makers play a crucial role in determining the structure and direction of the educational system. It is recommended that they advocate for investments in technology infrastructure at a policy level. Ensuring equitable access to quality educational technology resources supports the evolution of modern learning environments, aligning with the broader goal of providing accessible and innovative education.
10. Educational technology developers play an important part in influencing the technologies utilized in contemporary classrooms. To improve the overall user experience for learners, it is recommended that developers collaboratively address audio quality issues and improve material accessibility on technology-assisted learning platforms. This proactive approach ensures that educational resources are of superior quality and contribute to an effective and enriching learning experience.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers made sure that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by Holy Trinity College of General Santos City to avoid engaging in practices that may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those with whom he sought to conduct the research.

Informed Consent. Before embarking on the study, the researchers informed the participants on the objectives, the research process, and on how and what they benefited from the study.

Voluntary Participation. The researchers respected the rights of the respondents to voluntary participation and, in any case, their refusal to continue their participation at any time and for whatever reason during the conduct of the study.

Gender Sensitivity. In the conduct of this study, the researchers carefully observed gender equality and sensitivity among the respondents regarding sexual orientation. Thus, assuring the respondents to be free from any form of discrimination and abuse concerning sexuality.

Cultural Sensitivity. The researchers showed the utmost respect and considered the cultural background, practices, perceptions, and beliefs of the respondents while accomplishing the study. They were given equal attention and the opportunity to participate during the conduct of the study, regardless of whatever culture they may have.

Data Privacy. The researchers assured the respondents that the data gathered during the study were handled with the utmost anonymity, beneficence, and confidentiality and used for the sole purpose of the study.

Safety Protocols. The researchers ensured the health safety and security of all the respondents while conducting the study by strictly complying with the minimum health protocols stipulated by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) on Emerging Infectious Diseases. The researchers ensured that the research process did not yield negative effects on the physical, social, and psychological aspects of the respondents.

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